

EXPLORING THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE ARABIC LANGUAGE AND ISLAMIC VALUES EDUCATION (A.L.I.V.E.) PROGRAM: A MULTIPLE CASE STUDY

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Exploring the Implementation of the Arabic Language and Islamic Values Education (A.L.I.V.E.) Program: A Multiple Case Study

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to explore the implementation of Arabic Language and Islamic Values Education (ALIVE), specifically, it sought answers to the question: How do the participants view their experiences in the implementation of Arabic Language and Islamic Values Education (ALIVE) program? The study employed a qualitative multiple case research design. The participants of this study were the ALIVE learners of DepEd Palimbang District I, Palimbang, Sultan Kudarat. Purposive sampling was used in determining the participants of the study. The study had four formulated themes which were the best practices, benefits, opportunities, and similarities and differences in the implementation of ALIVE program. The following topics were developed by the best practices theme: creating a positive atmosphere, adopting moral principles, learning the Arabic language and alphabet, and using knowledge. The following emerging themes emerged from the benefits: educating about Islam, learning useful skills, and applying what was learned. The following themes have emerged as a result of the opportunities: socializing, self-development, and upgrading education. However, in order to assess its effectiveness in promoting Islamic principles and Arabic language competency, this study is crucial. This study provided insightful information about the program's effectiveness, room for improvement, and wider relevance in fostering religious education and cultural awareness in schools and society at large.

Keywords: *educational management, A.L.I.V.E. program, learners, implementation, multiple case study*

Introduction

“Never give up; Allah does not burden us beyond our capacities, so be thankful in every condition.”

-Darussalam

The quotation above by Darussalam explains that Allah (God) does not give human beings struggles and problems if they cannot overcome them. God is reliable; he will not allow people to be tested beyond their capacity, but amid their trial, he will also make a way for them to escape to withstand it. Islam in Nigeria is considered as a minority religion. Many Muslims are found in relatively poorer communities, especially those who do not receive the same services provided to the majority religion, like Christians. Muslim parents in these areas desire the best for their children: a good education combining religious and cultural foundations and essential skills for the modern world. They want their kids to feel secure and at ease at school. They are willing to spend whatever they can for good schools and teachers, regardless of their financial situation (Abdullah, 2018; Gamon & Tagoranao, 2022). However, despite the Philippine government's efforts to promote madrasah education, new educational obstacles have inevitably arisen in modern society. The evolving educational landscape provides a clear perspective for revising programs and policies necessary for madrasah education in the Philippines. In general, the common problems encountered when teaching in ALIVE are the following: Delayed Salary/honorarium; Lack of support from Local Government Units; Scarce and Limited books; Lack of classroom supplies and instructional materials in teaching ALIVE; Insufficient salaries/allowances provided by the Government; Lack of Training/Seminars in Teaching ALIVE; Lack of Qualified ALIVE teachers; Lack of Supervision from the DepEd (Sali & Ancho, 2021; van der Walt & Oosthuizen, 2021).

Moreover, the Philippines urges the development of healthy, moral, and spiritual citizens. Islamic education is essential for every Muslim to understand the world and life, a vital role to know right and wrong, according to the Islamic perspectives and their sense of responsibility in society. Muslims have intellectual and educational rights and can actively participate in the social, economic, and political spheres. There is an emphasis on the need for hermeneutics of Islamic education to establish a pedagogical framework responsive to current requirements (Abdullah, 2018; Bocca-Aldaqr, 2019).

Locally, a minority of Muslim learners face discrimination, which was previously a big problem. However, with the help of the ALIVE program and the Muslim Students Organization (M.S.O.), the problem was addressed through proper values education. The school needs to sustain these programs by showing the Muslim learners' beliefs, culture, and traditions to make them visible. Through this, other learners see the support administration and become more aware; in the process, Muslim learners can feel more accepted and respected; also, with the new generation, where pupils can no longer tell their culture, values, and practices of the past, which may eventually take a different path with their descendants. These pupils, too, are affected by the decreasing number of teachers and inadequate material resources (Ikhlas et al., 2021).

On the other hand, identified schools in Palimbang District have been implementing the Arabic Language and Islamic Values Education (A.L.I.V.E.) program. However, many communities and government agencies are only now beginning to grapple with the cultural and religious differences between schools. They are still waiting for a solution imposed from the outside, even if one exists. Instead, they require assistance in discussing strategies, presenting and testing competing ideas and techniques, and coming to a consensus on what works and what does not. The program aims to give Muslim pupils acceptable and relevant educational opportunities while considering their cultural backgrounds and unique reasons for participating (Milligan, 2018).

The urgency of conducting a research study on implementing the Arabic Language and Islamic Values Education (A.L.I.V.E.) program lies in its potential to address critical societal needs. With the increasing global significance of Arabic-speaking regions and the growing diversity of multicultural societies, understanding the impact and effectiveness of A.L.I.V.E. becomes paramount. This program aims to promote proficiency in Arabic and instill essential Islamic values, fostering a strong sense of cultural identity, tolerance, and intercultural understanding. Such research is urgently needed to evaluate the program's educational outcomes, social integration, and its ability to cultivate responsible global citizens equipped to navigate the complexities of our interconnected world, promoting peace, mutual respect, and cooperation among diverse communities.

Hence, this study is intended to be added to a trove of data that might help address the challenges ALIVE teachers and students face. The result could serve as the groundwork for a more in-depth understanding of the challenges in implementing the ALIVE program as an integral part of the educative process.

Research Questions

This multiple case study aimed to explore the implementation of Arabic Language and Islamic Values Education (ALIVE). Specifically, it sought answers to the question:

1. How do the participants view their experiences implementing the Arabic Language and Islamic Values Education (ALIVE) program?
2. What are the similarities and dissimilarities among the cases in terms of experiences, coping, and insights of the participants?

Methodology

This section explains the research approach used for this study. It includes the researcher's role, study subjects, data collection, data analysis, methodologies, credibility, and ethical considerations.

Research Design

This study used a qualitative method of multiple case studies to understand the topic of the implementation of the A.L.I.V.E. program through students from various schools that offer the program. It is a research design that allows for the exploration of a phenomenon in its context using a variety of data sources in which case study design is utilized to acquire an in-depth grasp of the circumstance and meaning for everyone concerned (Bazen et al., 2021).

Furthermore, qualitative research methods date back to the ancient Greek philosophers who used qualitative observation to analyze and describe the world around them. As a result, they are the oldest scientific approaches. A range of methods for methodically analyzing statistical or numerical data to study social phenomena is known as quantitative research design. Because of this, quantitative research is measurement-based and presupposes that the phenomena being examined can be measured. It seeks to evaluate the measurements and look for patterns and relationships in the data (Habib, 2021).

Moreover, non-numerical data (such as text, video, or audio) are gathered and analyzed in qualitative research to better understand concepts, beliefs, or experiences. It can be used to discover intricate details about a problem or generate fresh research concepts. Quantitative research involves gathering and analyzing numerical data for statistical analysis, while qualitative research does not. In fields like anthropology, sociology, education, the health sciences, and history, qualitative research is frequently employed in the humanities and social sciences.

Also, numerous techniques can be used to collect qualitative data, and a single qualitative study may use several techniques at different points in the data collection phase. The social science disciplines sociology, anthropology, and psychology are the foundation for qualitative research. In light of this, the qualitative research techniques enable detailed and additional probing and questioning of respondents. Additionally, the researcher or interviewer tries to comprehend their intentions and emotions. In order to conclude market research, it can be helpful to understand how their audience decides (Williams, 2019).

Henceforth, the focus is on the process rather than the outcome, the investigation rather than the confirmation, and the meaning rather than the variable. The implementation of the A.L.I.V.E. Program was the focus of this multi-case study. Trying to see the whole process via the lens of a single data point would only get part of the picture. Considering these considerations, the study's design of several cases was ideal. In this study, A.L.I.V.E. learners from various schools were used as individual cases, and each of them played a role in providing information about the A.L.I.V.E. Program's implementation, the similarities and differences between each case school, and the benefits that would be gained from it (Setiawan, 2020).

A qualitative approach is used if the purpose of the research is to gather data, which includes interview transcripts, audio recordings, field notes, diaries, personal comments, official records, and anything that can convey the actual words or actions of the people concerned in the study (Arifin, 2018). This study used multiple case studies to determine the level of impact of the ALIVE program on pupils in Palembang District I. Descriptive and critical analysis of the collected data was applied throughout the study. This study's textual material, such as the ALIVE monthly reports, was also used as a secondary source for data collection.

A qualitative case study is an approach to analysis that makes it easier to analyze a phenomenon using various data sources within its context. It means that the problem is not explored by one lens but rather by several lenses that make it possible to expose and appreciate several dimensions of the phenomenon. Accordingly, studying human interpretation of events or phenomena from actual happenings in the real world is also a case study. It is where the participants' experiences invoked in the study go deeper into their minds, defining the meaning of the experience through lengthy discussions expressed by the participants (Mohajan, 2018).

Moreover, case studies, one of the most popular qualitative research methods, investigate an individual, group, community, or establishment. A bounded theory approach is frequently used by researchers, which restricts the case study in terms of time or space. The researcher may use various data sources, including observation, interviews, and documents, to conduct the case study. All selected participants must be connected to the research question or topic being studied in some way, either directly or indirectly. I examined the data after gathering it to look for recurring or significant themes (Thomas, 2021).

Participants

The participants of this study were the ALIVE learners of DepEd Palimbang District I, Palimbang, Sultan Kudarat. Purposive sampling was utilized to determine the study participants. Purposive sampling is a qualitative research technique for identifying and selecting information-rich situations to efficiently use limited resources (Campbell et al., 2020). It entails locating and selecting individuals or groups who are exceptionally educated or experienced about a topic of interest (Creswell & Poth, 2016). In addition to knowledge and experience, experts emphasize the importance of availability and willingness to get involved and the ability to articulate, express, and reflect on experiences and ideas. Probabilistic or random sampling, on the other hand, is used to ensure the generalizability of findings by reducing the possibility of selection bias and controlling for the influence of known and unknown confounders.

The participants of this study were the students with the involvement of parents and stakeholders from the five (5) schools in Palembang District I that offer the ALIVE program. They underwent an in-depth interview (I.D.I.) for data collection, done online or through face-to-face interviews. A selected teacher, parents, stakeholders, and students also underwent the focus group discussion. The inclusion in this study was that those participants must be involved in A.L.I.V.E. Program and listed as A.L.I.V.E. present learners in the schools that provide ALIVE programs in DepEd Palimbang District 1, Palimbang, Sultan Kudarat. Data and information were collected during the data collection period only. The excluded from this study were those learners who were not enrolled in the ALIVE program and schools that have the ALIVE program but are not located in DepEd Palimbang District I, Palimbang, Sultan Kudarat. Furthermore, data and information outside the given timeframe were excluded.

Data Collection

Qualitative research interviews aim to comprehend the world from the subjects' perspective, clarify the significance of people's experiences, and reveal their lived reality before developing scientific interpretations. Further, qualitative research interviews unfold as an interviewer asks the interviewee questions to gather subjective information about a particular topic or experience (Quejada & Orale, 2018; Velmonte, 2020).

The individual collecting the data is crucial in qualitative research. Regardless of the subject area or preferred method for defining data (qualitative vs. quantitative), reliable data collection is crucial to upholding the integrity of the research. Choosing appropriate data-gathering tools (current, updated, or newly invented) and providing clear instructions for their proper usage decreases the risk of mistakes.

Before conducting the study, I asked permission from the Ethics and Review Committee and the Graduate School of Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Colleges. Upon approval, I asked permission to conduct the study through a formal letter to the Schools Division Superintendent of Sultan Kudarat Division, Sir Leonardo M. Balala, C.E.S.E. I then coordinated with the teachers involved in the study. After ensuring the rigor and appropriateness of the interview guide, the following data-gathering procedures were observed:

First was the preparation of the logistical requirements, including the venue and audio/voice recorder used during the interview with the participants. The venue and time were determined during my meeting via Zoom and face-to-face.

Moreover, before the interview, the participants were given a copy of the consent form to sign via Zoom and a physical meeting. It contained the study's objectives, methodology, confidentiality, and benefits, as well as my contact number for clarifications or verifications of the purpose. After which, with no more extended questions or clarifications, the Consent Forms were retrieved. A Participant Agreement Form followed it. It indicated the agreement between the participants and me for the interview and transcription process. It included the use of a pseudonym and other pertinent information to help me come to know and recall each participant. Most of all, the form included their permission to conduct the interview.

Further, it was followed by a one-on-one interview with the participants via Zoom and face-to-face. It consisted of two parts. The first part was a mere solicitation of information that would serve as the basis for the background of the participants. The second part was the interview proper, which consisted of questions on how the ALIVE learners view their experiences in implementing the ALIVE program in Palembang I District.

With the participants interviewed face-to-face, COVID-19 protocols were observed, for instance, following established protocols regarding mask-wearing, physical distancing, hand sanitizing, and other preventive measures.

Since the study utilized one-on-one interviews, building rapport and trust with the participants is more important than the questions in the discussion guide. The list of questions and objectives is meaningless if the participant feels self-conscious or apprehensive throughout the session. That is why I initiated a preliminary meeting with the informants and explained the study's details, making them understand that everything would be done with utmost confidentiality.

Then, I conducted one-on-one interviews with the participants at an agreed time and place at their convenience. A digital recorder was used to record the interview. Their answers in the interview were transcribed after the interview process. The participants were asked questions during the proper interview, followed by elucidating or probing questions. The main question is: How do the ALIVE learners view their experiences implementing the ALIVE program? Asking this grand tour question allowed the freedom to tell their stories without constraint. Sub-questions in the semi-structured interview guide were also asked to elicit specific experiences.

During the interview, prompt questions were used for clarification and focus. Prompt questions include when, who, where, why, how, and what. Prompt questions were intended to lead the participant but to encourage and elicit examples and meaning about the experience they are describing. Interviews were conducted at their respective homes free of interruption, like during their free time or after their busy hours, and conducive to reflective storytelling. Each participant will be interviewed separately at different times. The length of interviews may or may not last for about an hour.

At the end of the interview, a leading question was asked: "Was there any experience that was not asked that you would like to share?" In most instances, this question did not elicit any new information. I recorded the interviews on audio, wrote an exact transcription, and used member verification to confirm the information. Participants are assured of confidentiality, as explicated in the section of the informed consent form for human consideration. Field notes were taken during the interview to record body language or other contributing factors not reflected in the recording. It was done to minimize distractions to the participant. Moreover, after the interviews, I transcribed the audio recordings as soon as possible. Member checking was used as a method of validation whereby participants read and affirmed the contents of the interview transcript by affixing their signatures. Such a validation process signaled the trustworthiness of the data. The interview saturation point is identified when the tenor of the answers has the same flow of thought deriving from the same phenomenon of experiences based on the similarity of experiences revealed during the interview.

Data Analysis

In order to reduce the distance between themselves and the participants in a qualitative study, researchers work to become as close to the participants as possible (Creswell & Poth, 2016). In a research project, it is essential to distill the vast amount of data gathered and express the critical findings while presenting the findings. The approach used to evaluate the data comprised data reduction, data visualization, conclusion, inference, and verification. Qualitative content analysis is "any qualitative material and attempts to identify core consistencies and meanings."

The Colaizzi process for phenomenological data analysis, as outlined by Hunt et al. (2020), involves several steps. Initially, researchers read the transcript multiple times to grasp the overall content, extracting significant statements related to the phenomenon and noting their location. Subsequently, meanings are formulated from these statements, with researchers bracketing pre-suppositions to stay true to the experienced phenomenon. These meanings are sorted into categories, clusters, and themes, carefully avoiding pre-existing theoretical influences. Next, the findings are integrated into an exhaustive description presented as a narrative account, incorporating emergent themes and meanings to explore the experience comprehensively. Finally, researchers describe the fundamental structure of the phenomenon, thus completing the analytical process.

The participants themselves should validate the findings to match my descriptive results with the study participants' experiences. I asked the participants if the text accurately portrays their experience, and based on this input, I changed earlier parts of the analysis.

Ethical Considerations

For this qualitative study, a critical ethical factor has specific ramifications. These problems and worries mainly result from the approach used in this study. In particular, about the population and data, the R.M.M.C. Ethics and Review Committee's standards for ethical consideration were fulfilled in this study, including but not limited to:

Voluntary Participation. The participants were free to participate without fear of consequences, loss of benefits, or compensation plans. Therefore, the participant's rights to contribute to the body of knowledge were carefully considered and anticipated when the study's objective and advantages were explained to the participant. The participants in this study were not coerced into taking part. Individuals who become uncomfortable while doing the survey can end their participation.

Privacy and confidentiality. Participants' privacy rights shall not be violated without their informed agreement under the current Data Privacy Act of 2012, which safeguards this fundamental human right. Allowing participants to omit their names from the interview guide is one technique to maintain privacy and confidentiality in this quantitative study. In addition, confidentiality and privacy were preserved by withholding the informants' personal information, such as their age, gender, occupation, and health conditions. As a result, their identity was kept private for security reasons.

Informed consent process. Given the investigation's limitations, the potential research volunteers were adequately informed about the study's goals, procedures, and advantages. The participants' affirmative response demonstrates that the request for their involvement was voluntary. The informed consent form required participants to sign to indicate that they freely chose to participate in the study. The participants' identities were not listed on the survey form, and their responses were kept private. The participants knew they could withdraw from participating in the study anytime.

Recruitment. The participants were informed of why they had become part of the study. For the participants to understand the study, I explained its purpose so they could further infer from it and view its essence. Apart from the letter, I gave the rationale of the research and its significance.

Risks. If the benefit-risk ratio is acceptable and favorable, research will be done. This study's need to protect the participants from significant harm is equally essential. The study prioritized the welfare of the participants. Furthermore, the participants were not harmed since their identities were held confidential. Their security and safety were of the utmost concern. As the researcher, I must ensure that the participants are physically, emotionally, and socially ready. In answering the interview guide, I confirmed that the participants did not feel discomfort or awkwardness.

Benefits. The participants in this study profited from the results, which offered insightful information about their experiences, difficulties, and coping mechanisms throughout this historical period. Implementing the ALIVE program is globally significant as it promotes the integration of the Arabic language and Islamic values, fostering cultural preservation, interfaith dialogue, and enhancing Islamic education. The findings of the study hold importance for various stakeholders: the Department of Education can use them to guide policy implementation and support pupils with learning struggles; national, regional, provincial, and city managers can utilize them for planning and monitoring ALIVE activities in their areas; school heads and teachers can improve learning outcomes and adjust their approaches accordingly; parents and communities gain insights into students' perceptions of Islam, enabling them to support the program and strengthen partnerships; students themselves deepen their understanding of Islamic views and receive guidance on learning plans; and future researchers can utilize the study as a contribution to the teaching profession and as a guide for assessing the ALIVE program's implementation.

Plagiarism. There was no hint or proof that the research had misinterpreted someone else's work. Grammarly and other plagiarism checkers were used in the study. I must possess integrity and good character, which come with moral principles and values, to work as a researcher. For my research article to be seen as genuine, I need to be more knowledgeable about the paradigm of plagiarism.

Fabrication. The report did not hint or provide evidence that the work had been intentionally misinterpreted. There was no fabrication of information or outcomes or deliberate presentation of incorrect conclusions. I employed and integrated theories related to the information and other inferential concepts.

Falsification. The study did not indicate overclaiming or exaggeration, and it did not intentionally mislead the work for theoretical expectations. Furthermore, this study needed to follow the guidelines for data manipulation, which include making claims based on incomplete information or omitting crucial elements, as well as using materials, equipment, or techniques that might deceive others.

Conflict of Interest (C.O.I.). There was no indication of a conflict of interest in the study, like disclosure of C.O.I. or circumstances where professional judgment on the principal appeal is required. Conflict of interest is similar to monetary academic advantages or recognitions and tends to influence participants' welfare or the research's validity. In addition, the participants were coerced into participating in the study by me, who had no control or influence over them.

Deceit. The study did not mislead the participants about any possible danger. Since the participants in any inquiry have completed higher education, their rights must be enormously safeguarded; thus, reasonable and acceptable guidelines must be followed.

Permission from Organization/Location. I followed protocols. Upon receiving the panelists' signal, the adviser, and the committee of the R.M.M.C.E.R.C., I sought approval from the school division Superintendents for the conduct of the study through a formal letter. Following this, I composed an official letter and included the school's letter of support from the superintendent of the school's division to the district supervisor and principal of the participating schools in the study. The ALIVE learners who were part of the study were oriented before administering the interview guide.

Authorship. I ensured that research outputs were fair, transparent, and accurately represented the contributions of all those involved. By adhering to ethical authorship practices, research outputs maintained their credibility and contributed to advancing knowledge fairly and transparently.

Results

This portion contains the study's findings from the interview of the learners' experiences implementing the Arabic Language and Islamic Values Education (A.L.I.V.E.) program.

Description of the Participants

The study participants were five learners from different Palimbang 1 District, Division of Sultan Kudarat schools.

Case 1 – Alpha is a male, 11 years old, Grade 6 learner of Palimbang Central School who is currently enrolled in the Arabic Language and Islamic Values Education (A.L.I.V.E.) program.

Case 2 – Bravo is a 12-year-old female, a Grade 6 learner of Langali Integrated School,, currently enrolled in the Arabic Language and Islamic Values Education (A.L.I.V.E.) program.

Case 3 – Charlie is a female, 11-year-old, Grade 6 learner of Kanipaan Elementary School currently enrolled in the Arabic Language and Islamic Values Education (A.L.I.V.E.) program.

Case 4 – Delta is a 12-year-old male, Grade 6 learner of Barongis Elementary School, currently enrolled in the Arabic Language and Islamic Education Values (A.L.I.V.E.) program.

Case 5 – Echo is a 12-year-old male, Grade 6 learner of Wasag Elementary School, who is currently enrolled in the Arabic Language and Islamic Values Education (A.L.I.V.E.) program.

The participants were asked questions during the interview, followed by clarifying or probing questions. This kind of open-ended grand tour inquiry allowed people to share their tales without being constrained. Sub-questions included in the semi-structured interview guide were also asked to elicit particular experiences. I guaranteed each informant anonymity and non-disclosure. The disclosures from the study's five examples are consistent with one another.

The five participants involved in the case study were Alpha, Bravo, Charlie, Delta, and Echo (all pseudonyms). The following chapters present a detailed description of the five cases.

Additionally, these code names, drawn from the NATO phonetic alphabet, add a layer of security and professionalism to the research process, enhancing the credibility and integrity of the study. These pseudonyms provide anonymity and confidentiality, safeguarding the students' privacy while allowing researchers to refer to them in discussions and analyses without revealing their identities. Also, using distinct and easily distinguishable code names facilitates organization and clarity in data collection and analysis, reducing the likelihood of confusion or misinterpreting findings. Employing such pseudonyms ensures both the protection of participants' identities and the effectiveness of the research endeavor in the ALIVE program context.

4. CASE 1-ALPHA

Alpha is an 11-year-old male, a Grade 6 learner at Palembang Central School, currently enrolled in the Arabic Language and Islamic Values Education (A.L.I.V.E.) program.

Best Practices of the Schools in the Implementation of A.L.I.V.E. Program

The table below describes the essential themes gathered about the schools' best practices in implementing the A.L.I.V.E. program. Moreover, core ideas are also presented based on the responses of the Alpha participants.

Developing Conducive Environment

A conducive environment is essential for fostering growth, learning, and innovation. Whether in educational institutions, workplaces, or communities, creating a supportive and encouraging atmosphere empowers individuals to thrive, collaborate, and achieve their fullest potential (Abram et al., 2020).

It is evident in the verbatim as follows:

Ang pagbibigay sa akin at sa iba pang mga mag-aaral ng magagandang halaga na maaaring lumikha ng magandang pakiramdam ng pagkakaisa patungo sa multi-cultural na komunidad. (Participant 1, lines 43-45)

Giving me and other students good values that can create a good sense of unity in the multi-cultural community.

Magkaroon sana ng sariling classroom at prayer room para mahusay ang pagtuturo ng A.L.I.V.E teacher. (Participant 1, lines 38-39)

I would like to have my own classroom and prayer room so that the A.L.I.V.E teacher can teach well.

Adapting Good Values

Adapting good values is a fundamental aspect of personal and societal development. Embracing ethical principles, empathy, respect,

and compassion contributes to individual well-being and cultivates a harmonious and compassionate community where people can coexist positively and constructively. Commitment to good values guides decision-making, fostering stronger relationships and promoting a healthier and more prosperous society (Godoy, 2018).

He replied:

Bukod sa natutunan ko sa literary at numeracy competencies, nagawa kong mapanatili ang mabuting moral sa iba. Tulad ng paggalang sa pagkakaiba-iba. A.L.I.V.E. Ang programa ay isa sa programa ng DepEd na tunay na hulma sa akin sa pamamagitan ng pagtuturo sa tunay na paraan at mabuting paraan ng isang Muslim (Participant 1, lines 66-68)

Aside from the literary and numeracy competencies learned, I maintained good morals towards others. Like respecting diversity. The ALIVE program was one of the DepEd programs that genuinely molded me by educating the natural way and good ways of a Muslim.

Pinakamahasay ay yong tinuturuan kami sa bahay magbasa ng Arabic at mag-memorize ng mga Surah or verses sa Qur-an. (Participant 1, lines 69-70)

What is the best is to teach us at home to read Arabic and memorize Surahs or verses from the Qur-an.

Learning Arabic Alphabet and Language

Learning the Arabic alphabet and language opens doors to a rich cultural heritage and facilitates more profound connections with millions of Arabic speakers worldwide. Beyond the linguistic benefits, it offers insights into Islamic traditions, literature, and history, enabling a greater appreciation and understanding of this diverse and influential global language (Sali & Ancho, 2021).

Alpha replied:

Pinalawak ang aking pang-unawa sa iba't ibang indibidwal sa mga tuntunin ng multi-kultural at pagkakaiba-iba. Nakapagbigay ako ng magagandang halaga na tutulong sa akin na makihalubilo at bumuo ng magandang relasyon sa iba. (Participant 1, lines 47-50)

Expanded my understanding of different individuals in terms of multi-cultural and diversity. I instilled good values to help me socialize and build good relationships with others.

Ang aking pinakamahasay na kasanayan sa programang A.L.I.V.E ay ang pagkatoto ng Arabic Language kung paano sumulat at bumasa ng mga mag-aaral at aking naituro ang kaugalian ng propheta Muhammad (peace be upon him). (Participant 1, lines 71-73)

My best practice in the A.L.I.V.E program is to teach the Arabic Language how to read and write to the students and I was able to teach the custom of the prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him).

Applying Knowledge

Applying knowledge is the bridge that connects learning to meaningful action. By actively using the information and skills we acquire, we can solve problems, innovate, and positively impact our lives and the world. The practical application of knowledge empowers individuals to grow personally and professionally, contributing to a more informed and progressive society (Kooria, 2022).

The following was seen in the verbatim:

Pagsasanay at paglalapat ng lahat ng mga pagpapahalagang itinuro araw-araw. (Participant 1, lines 36-37)

Equipping and applying all the values taught everyday.

The benefits of the A.L.I.V.E. program

The table explains the essential theme of the A.L.I.V.E. program's benefits, as gathered by Alpha's answers regarding its implementation.

Islam Teaching

Islam's teachings encompass a comprehensive set of principles and values that guide individuals in leading righteous and purposeful lives. With a focus on faith, compassion, and social responsibility, Islam's teachings promote spiritual growth, moral development, and harmonious coexistence, fostering a sense of unity and understanding among diverse communities worldwide. As individuals embrace these teachings, they strive to embody the values of kindness, justice, and humility, positively contributing to their communities and fostering a more compassionate and interconnected global society (Harad & Arriola, 2022).

It is evident in the verbatim as follows:

Pinalawak ang aking pang-unawa sa iba't ibang indibidwal sa mga tuntunin ng multi-kultural at pagkakaiba-iba.

Nakapagbigay ako ng magagandang halaga na tutulong sa akin na makihalubilo at bumuo ng magandang relasyon sa iba. (Participant 1, lines 47-50)

Expanded my understanding of different individuals in terms of multi-cultural and diversity. It instilled good values to help me socialize and build good relationships with others.

Sa pamamagitan ng kanilang pagkatoto sa panawagan ng Islam. (A2 Participant 1, lines 148)

Through their obedience to the call of Islam.

Natutunan ko ang turo ng Islam, Kalinisan, pagiging magalang, makatao, makabayan, pagiging matakutin sa Allah, Mapagkumbaba at palagi ang pagbabalik-loob sa kanya (Tawbah). Mga kwento ng lahat ng Propheta sa kung saan lahat sila ay nagpatirapa sa Allah. (A2 Participant 1, lines 167-168)

I learned the teachings of Islam, Cleanliness, being respectful, humane, patriotic, fearing Allah, Humility and always turning to him (Tawbah).

Pag-iingat alinsunod sa sinabi ng Allah (Nisa:71) "Oh kayo mga naniniwala, mag-ingat kayo." upang hindi magkasakit ay dapat na pag-ingat. (A2 Participant 1, lines 161-162)

Stories of all the Prophets in which they all prostrated to Allah. Caution according to what Allah said (Nisa:71) "O you who believe, be careful." to not get sick should be careful.

Learn Valuable Strategies

Learning valuable strategies equips individuals with essential tools to navigate challenges, achieve goals, and make informed decisions. In education, career, or personal development, acquiring effective strategies empowers individuals to overcome obstacles, optimize their strengths, and adapt to ever-changing circumstances. Finding and using proper techniques regularly improves one's capacity for problem-solving, fosters personal development, and increases self-efficacy, all of which open doors to success and happiness in various spheres of life (Isah & Base, 2022).

The following is seen in the verbatim:

Isa sa mga pagtuturo ng programang A.L.I.V.E ay ang pagiging matatag at optimistiko. Kaya, ang pagharap sa araw-araw ay hindi kasing tamis ng kahapon, dahil ang bawat araw ay isang hamon na dapat harapin. Kaya, bilang isang mag-aaral ng A.L.I.V.E ay nagpapasalamat ako na mayroon akong mga katangiang nakakatulong sa aking pang-araw-araw na buhay (Participant 1, lines 65-69)

One of the teachings of the ALIVE program is to be steadfast and optimistic. Thus, facing every day is not as sweet as yesterday, because every day is challenging. Thus, as a student of ALIVE, I was thankful that I have been equipped with the traits that help in my day-to-day life.

Makinig sa klase, magsikap sa pag-aaral. (A2, line 157)

Listen in class, work hard in studying

Application of Learning

The application of learning is the key to unlocking the true potential of knowledge. When we actively apply what we have learned through practical experiences or real-world scenarios, we deepen our understanding, refine our skills, and reinforce our memory. By using our knowledge in meaningful ways, we enrich our lives and contribute to the betterment of society, driving progress, innovation, and positive change in the world around us (Puskás & Andersson, 2019).

He replied as follows:

Ang aking kwentong pandemya. Tulad ng alam natin sa panahon ng pandemya, napakaraming mga paghihigpit at panuntunan na dapat sundin. Kaya, dapat kang maging laging pasensya at sumunod sa mga alituntunin dahil lahat ng iyong gagawin ay may mga kahihinatnan na maaaring makaapekto sa kalusugan ng iyong pamilya (Participant 1, lines 72-76).

My pandemic story. As we know during the pandemic, there are many restrictions and rules to follow. So you must always be patient and obey the rules because everything you do will have consequences that might affect your family's health.

Sa pamamagitan ng pagsagawa ng lahat ng aking napag-aralan sa A.L.I.V.E tulad ng pagsuot ng Hijab at pagdarasal ng limang beses sa isang araw. (A3, lines 255-256)

By doing everything I learned in A.L.I.V.E like wearing Hijab and praying five times a day

The Opportunities to Improve the Implementation of the A.L.I.V.E. Program

The table below discusses the essential theme of the opportunities to improve the implementation of the ALIVE program.

Upgrade Education

Upgrade education is a vital endeavor that involves continuous improvement and innovation in teaching methodologies, curricula, and educational systems. By incorporating cutting-edge technologies, fostering critical thinking, and promoting creativity, upgrading education equips students with the skills needed to thrive in a rapidly evolving world. This approach not only enhances individual learning outcomes but also contributes to the advancement of society (Nurzannah et al., 2020).

Alpha said:

Deployment ng mas maraming A.L.I.V.E teachers para maabot ang mag-aaral na walang access sa programang ito lalo na sa mga liblib na paaralan. (Participant 1, lines 79-80)

Deploy more ALIVE teachers to reach learners without access to this program, especially in the secluded schools.

Seminar at mag-aaral ng mabuti upang matugunan ang mga hamon sa buhay. (A2, line 178)

Seminar and study well to meet life's challenges

Self-Development

Self-development is a lifelong personal growth and improvement journey, encompassing acquiring new knowledge, skills, and perspectives. By actively investing in self-awareness, setting meaningful goals, and embracing challenges, individuals can unlock their full potential, cultivate resilience, and lead more fulfilling and purposeful lives. The process of self-development empowers individuals to become the best version of themselves, contributing positively to their well-being and making a meaningful impact on the world around them (Ayangco-Derramas, 2022).

It is evident in the verbatim as follows:

Sa pagiging huwaran sa ibang estudyante. Ibabahagi ko rin sa kanila ang mga benepisyo ng pag-aaral ng programang ito. Sa ganitong paraan matutulungan ko ang programa sa pagpapatupad nito. (Participant 1, lines 83-85)

By being a role model to other students. I will also share with them the benefits of learning this program. In this way, I could help the program in its implementation. The best practices I can share with other students are the teachings and values I learned from the ALIVE program.

Socialization

The basic socialization process is how people pick up and assimilate their community's customs, beliefs, and actions. It is essential for forming a person's identity, social skills, and capacity to function in various social situations. Individuals build relationships, foster empathy, and develop a sense of belonging by engaging in social interactions, ultimately contributing to the cohesiveness and harmony of communities and societies (Fadhilaatika, 2022).

The following is seen in the verbatim:

Pinalawak ang aking pang-unawa sa iba't ibang indibidwal sa mga tuntunin ng multi-kultural at pagkakaiba-iba. Nakapagbigay ako ng magagandang halaga na tutulong sa akin na makihalubilo at bumuo ng magandang relasyon sa iba (Participant 1, lines 47, 50).

Expanded my understanding of different individuals in terms of multi-cultural and diversity. I instilled good values that will help me socialize and build good relationships with others.

Sa pamamagitan ng pag-participate, commitment or kailangang sincere sa programang ito. (A2, lines 174-175)

By participating, commitment or sincerity in this program.

Table 1. *Best Practices, Benefits, and Opportunities to Improve the School in the Implementation of the ALIVE Program*

<i>Clustered Themes</i>	<i>Emergent Themes</i>
Best Practices	
Teachers should have a personal classroom.	Developing Conductive Environment
A personal prayer room would be of great help in delivering quality education.	
Show good morals towards others	Adapting Good Values
Respect diversity of culture, belief, and religion	
Encouraged to read Arabic and memorize Surah or verses of Qur-an	
Arabic Alphabet and Language	Learning Arabic Alphabet and Language
Learned to read the Arabic alphabet	
Apply the values that they have learned in the ALIVE program	Applying Knowledge

Practice what they had learned even outside the school premises	
Benefits	
Able to share the Islamic teaching with the learners	
A to value the Islam teaching more	Islam Teaching
Have discovered a lot of valuable insights related to Islam teaching	
Able to learn about the history of the prophets and the value of Islam	
Learned many strategies like how to become hardworking, persistent, patient, and other good qualities	Learn Valuable Strategies
Were taught how to study hard and do their best while learning the ALIVE program	
We're able to apply their learning in real-life situations	
Applied the teachings in the ALIVE program, like wearing their Hijab properly and praying constantly	Application of Learning
Learned to abide by the rules and regulations set by the school through the help of the ALIVE program	
Opportunities to Improve	
Help learners achieve excellent quality of education	
Expose ALIVE teachers to training and seminars	Upgrade Education
Hire more qualified ALIVE teachers	
Help learners strive to become a good role model	
Develop intrapersonal skills	Self-Development
Develop oneself by helping others and showing respect	
Maintain collaborative relationships	Socialization
Reach-out with others	

5. CASE 2 - BRAVO

Bravo is a 12-year-old female, Grade 6 learner of Langali Integrated School who is currently enrolled in the Arabic Language and Islamic Values Education (A.L.I.V.E.) program.

Best practices of the schools in the implementation of the A.L.I.V.E Program

The table below describes the essential themes gathered about the schools' best practices in implementing the A.L.I.V.E. program. Moreover, core ideas are also presented based on the participants' responses.

Developing Conducive Environment

A conducive environment is essential for fostering growth, learning, and innovation. Whether in educational institutions, workplaces, or communities, creating a supportive and encouraging atmosphere empowers individuals to thrive, collaborate, and achieve their fullest potential (van der Walt & Oosthuizen, 2021).

The following is seen in the verbatim:

Magkaroon sana ng sariling classroom at prayer room para mahusay ang pagtuturo ng A.L.I.V.E teacher (Participant 2, lines 125-126)

I wish ALIVE would have its own classroom and prayer room so that ALIVE can teach well teacher.

Cleaning the room of A.L.I.V.E class, *pag-aaral ng Qur-an at pag-aaral kung paano sumulat ng Arabic Alphabet.* (B5, lines 380-381)

Cleaning the room of A.L.I.V.E class, studying the Qur'an and learning how to write the Arabic Alphabet

Adapting Good Values

Adapting good values is a fundamental aspect of personal and societal development. Embracing ethical principles, empathy, respect, and compassion contributes to individual well-being and cultivates a harmonious and compassionate community where people can coexist positively and constructively. Commitment to good values guides decision-making, fostering stronger relationships and promoting a healthier and more prosperous society (Fuadi & Suyatno, 2020).

She replied the following:

Pinakamahusay ay yong tinuturuan kami sa bahay magbasa ng Arabic at mag-memorize ng mga Surah or verses sa Qur-an (Participant 2, lines 132-134)

The best is to teach us at home to read Arabic and memorize Surahs or verses from the Qur'an. The good practices I have experienced as a student of the ALIVE program are like teaching us to recognize the one creator (Allah).

Natutunan ko ang mabuting asal ng Islam at nalalaman ko kung ano ang ipinagbabawal sa Islam. Natuto mag-aral sa turo ng Islam maging mabuting Muslim. (B5, lines 386-387)

I have learned the good manners of Islam and I know what is forbidden in Islam. Learn to study the teachings of Islam to be a good Muslim

Learning Arabic Alphabet and Language

Learning the Arabic alphabet and language opens doors to a rich cultural heritage and facilitates more profound connections with millions of Arabic speakers worldwide. Beyond the linguistic benefits, it offers insights into Islamic traditions, literature, and history, enabling a greater appreciation and understanding of this diverse and influential global language (Harad & Arriola, 2022).

Bravo said:

Natutunan ko ang turo ng Islam, Kalinisan, pagiging magalang, makatao, Makabayan, pagiging matakutin sa Allah, Mapagkumbaba at palagi ang pagbabalik-loob sa kanya (Tawbah) (Participant 2, lines 150-152).

I learned the teachings of Islam: Cleanliness, being polite, humane, Patriotic, fearing Allah, Humility, and always turning to him (Tawbah).

Nasasanay ako kung paano sumulat at bumasa na Arabic alphabet (B5, line 383)

I am learning how to write and read the Arabic alphabet

Pagtuturo ng subject na Arabic language and Islamic values (B5, line 377)

Teaching the subject Arabic language and Islamic values

Applying Knowledge

Applying knowledge is the bridge that connects learning to meaningful action. By actively using the information and skills we acquire, we can solve problems, innovate, and positively impact our lives and the world. The practical application of knowledge empowers individuals to grow personally and professionally, contributing to a more informed and progressive society (Puskás & Andersson, 2019).

It is evident in the verbatim as follows:

Naghahanda ako, nananalangin sa Allah at sinasamahan ko ng pagsisikap sa aking pag-aaral. (Participant 2, lines 145-146)

I prepare, pray to Allah and put effort into my studies.

Lahat ng natutunan ko sa A.L.I.V.E ay ginawa ko tulad ng pagbigkas ng Bismillah bako ako matulog, kumain, maligo at iba pa. (B4, lines 323-324)

Everything I learned in A.L.I.V.E I did like reciting Bismillah I didn't sleep, eat, take a bath and so on.

The Benefits of the A.L.I.V.E Program

The table explains the essential theme of the benefits of the A.L.I.V.E. program that the answers of Bravo have gathered in implementing the A.L.I.V.E

program.

Islam Teaching

Islam's teachings encompass a comprehensive set of principles and values that guide individuals in leading righteous and purposeful lives. With a focus on faith, compassion, and social responsibility, Islam's teachings promote spiritual growth, moral development, and harmonious coexistence, fostering a sense of unity and understanding among diverse communities worldwide. As individuals embrace these teachings, they strive to embody the values of kindness, justice, and humility, positively contributing to their communities and fostering a more compassionate and interconnected global society (Shafaghat et al., 2018).

The following is seen in the verbatim:

Natutunan ko ang turo ng Islam, Kalinisan, pagiging magalang, makatao, Makabayan, pagiging matakutin sa Allah, Mapagkumbaba at palagi ang pagbabalik-loob sa kanya (Tawbah). *Pag-iingat alinsunod sa sinabi ng Allah* (Nisa: 71) (Participant 2, lines 150-152)

Through their obedience to the call of Islam. I learned the teachings of Islam: Cleanliness, being respectful, humane, Patriotic, being afraid of Allah, Humble, and always turning to him (Tawbah). Stories of all the Prophets in which they all prostrated to Allah. Caution

according to what Allah said (Nisa:71):

Oh kayo mga naniniwala, mag-ingat kayo." upang hindi magkasakit ay dapat nap ag-ingat (Participant 2, lines 161-162)

O you who believe, be careful." not to get sick should be careful.

Learn Valuable Strategies

Learning valuable strategies equips individuals with essential tools to navigate challenges, achieve goals, and make informed decisions. In education, career, or personal development, acquiring effective strategies empowers individuals to overcome obstacles, optimize their strengths, and adapt to ever-changing circumstances. Continuously seeking and applying valuable strategies enhances one's problem-solving abilities and leads to personal growth and a greater sense of self-efficacy, ultimately paving the way for success and fulfillment in various aspects of life (Sali & Marasigan, 2020).

She replied the following verbatim:

Makinig sa klase, magsikap sap ag aaral. (Participant 2, lines 157)

Listen in class, and work hard in studying.

Maging masipag sa pag-aral para may ginhawa ang pamumuhay. (B5, line 411)

Be diligent in studying so that life can be comfortable

Application of Learning

The application of learning is the key to unlocking the true potential of knowledge. When we actively apply what we have learned through practical experiences or real-world scenarios, we deepen our understanding, refine our skills, and reinforce our memory (Al Shlowiy, 2022).

It is evident in the verbatim as follows:

Isinasambuhay ko ang aking mga natutunan. (Participant 2, lines 164)

I apply what I have learned.

Pag-aaral ng mabuti para maganda ang kinabukasan.. (B4, line 303)

Study well for a bright future.

Mag-aaral ng Mabuti sa A.L.I.V.E para hindi ka maging ignorante sa Islam (B4, line 344)

Study well in A.L.I.V.E so you don't become ignorant of Islam.

The opportunities to improve the implementation of the A.L.I.V.E program

Upgrade Education

Upgrade education is a vital endeavor that involves continuous improvement and innovation in teaching methodologies, curricula, and educational systems. Upgrade education equips students with the skills needed to thrive in a rapidly evolving world by incorporating cutting-edge technologies, fostering critical thinking, and promoting creativity (Godoy, 2018).

She said:

Mag-aaral ng mabuti upang matugunan ang mga hamon sa buhay. (Participant 2, lines 178)

Study well to meet life's challenges.

Dagdagan ang aming mga A.L.I.V.E materials para makapagsikap kami lalo sa pag-aaral. (B4, lines 351-352)

Increase our A.L.I.V.E materials so we can work harder in learning.

May mga A.L.I.V.E modules po kami. (B4, line 355)

We have A.L.I.V.E modules.

May sariling classroom kami sana para makapag-aral kami ng maayos. (B4, lines 368-369)

I wish we had our own classroom so we could study properly

Self-Development

Self-development is a lifelong personal growth and improvement journey, encompassing acquiring new knowledge, skills, and perspectives. By actively investing in self-awareness, setting meaningful goals, and embracing challenges, individuals can unlock their

full potential, cultivate resilience, and lead more fulfilling and purposeful lives. The process of self-development empowers individuals to become the best version of themselves, contributing positively to their well-being and making a meaningful impact on the world around them (Abdulkarim & Suud, 2020).

The following is seen in the verbatim:

Ang pagiging aktibo sa klase at naga participate. (Participant 2, lines 196)

Being active in class and participative.

Pagkatuto mula sa mga modules na ibinibigay ng mga A.L.I.V.E teachers. (B5, lines 415-416)

Learning from modules provided by A.L.I.V.E teachers

Socialization

Socialization is the basic process by which people pick up and assimilate their community's customs, beliefs, and actions. It is essential for forming a person's identity, social skills, and capacity to function in various social situations. Individuals build relationships, foster empathy, and develop a sense of belonging by engaging in social interactions, ultimately contributing to the cohesiveness and harmony of communities and societies (Gomez et al., 2019).

This is evident in the verbatim as follows:

Ang aking mungkahi na maari kong ibahagi sa ibang mag-aaral upang matiyak ang mahusay na paghahatid ng mga serbisyo sa paaralan na A.L.I.V.E program ay pangalagaan at susuportahan natin ang programng ito (Participant 2, lines 197-199)

My suggestion that I can share with other students to ensure the efficient delivery of services in the school A.L.I.V.E program is that we will take care of and support this program.

Para mapabuti ang programang A.L.I.V.E magkaisa at magtulungan po. Makakatulong ako s pagpapatupad ng ikabubuti ng A.L.I.V.E kung ipamahagi ko din sa iba ang mga magagandang natutunan ko nito. Tinutulungan ako ng mga kapatid ko sa bahay paano magbasa ng A.L.I.V.E subject. (B6)

To improve the A.L.I.V.E program, please unite and work together. I will help implement the good of A.L.I.V.E if I also share the good things I learned with others. My siblings help me at home how to read A.L.I.V.E subject

Table 2. *Best Practices, Benefits, and Opportunities to Improve the School in the Implementation of the ALIVE Program*

<i>Clustered Themes</i>	<i>Emergent Themes</i>
Best Practices	
Teachers should have a personal classroom.	Developing Conductive Environment
A personal prayer room would be of great help in delivering quality education.	
Show good morals towards others	Adapting Good Values
Respect diversity of culture, belief, and religion	
Encouraged to read Arabic and memorize Surah or verses of Qur-an	Learning Arabic Alphabet and Language
Arabic Alphabet and Language	
Learned to read the Arabic alphabet	Applying Knowledge
Apply the values that they have learned in the ALIVE program	
Practice what they had learned even outside the school premises	
Benefits	
Able to share the Islamic teaching with the learners	Islam Teaching
A to value the Islam teaching more	
Have discovered a lot of valuable insights related to Islam teaching	Learn Valuable Strategies
Able to learn about the history of the prophets and the value of Islam	
Learned many strategies like how to become hardworking, persistent, patient, and other good qualities	
Were taught how to study hard and do their best while learning the ALIVE program	Application of Learning
We're able to apply their learning in real-life situations	
Applied the teachings in the ALIVE program, like wearing their Hijab properly and praying constantly	
Learned to abide by the rules and regulations set by the school through the help of the ALIVE program	
Opportunities to Improve	
Help learners achieve excellent quality of education	Upgrade Education
Expose ALIVE teachers to training and seminars	
Hire more qualified ALIVE teachers	Self-Development
Help learners strive to become a good role model	
Develop intrapersonal skills	
Develop oneself by helping others and showing respect	

Maintain collaborative relationships
Reach-out with others

Socialization

6. CASE 3 - CHARLIE

Charlie is an 11-year-old female Grade 6 learner at Kanipaan Elementary School enrolled in the Arabic Language and Islamic Values Education (A.L.I.V.E.) program.

Best Practices of the Schools in the Implementation of A.L.I.V.E Program

The table below describes the essential themes gathered about the schools' best practices in implementing the A.L.I.V.E. program. Moreover, core ideas are also presented based on the responses of the Charlie participant.

Developing Conducive Environment

A conducive environment is essential for fostering growth, learning, and innovation. Whether in educational institutions, workplaces, or communities, creating a supportive and encouraging atmosphere empowers individuals to thrive, collaborate, and achieve their fullest potential (Rosyada, 2021).

Charlie answered the following:

Ang pinakamahasay na kagawian ng paaralan sa pagpapatupad nito ay ang pagtuturo ng isang A.L.I.V.E teacher ng Arabic Language and Islamic Values Education sa pamamagitan ng modular sa panahon ng pandemya (Participant 3, lines 203-205).

A school's best practice for implementing the ALIVE program is having an ALIVE Teacher teaching Arabic Language and Islamic Values Education through modular during pandemic.

Adapting Good Values

Adapting good values is a fundamental aspect of personal and societal development. Embracing ethical principles, empathy, respect, and compassion contributes to individual well-being and cultivates a harmonious and compassionate community where people can coexist positively and constructively. Commitment to good values guides decision-making, fostering stronger relationships and promoting a healthier and more prosperous society (Mubarak, 2021).

It is evident in the verbatim as follows:

Nakakatulong ako sa pamamagitan ng pagsunod at pagsusuot ng Hijab O tandong para maipakita na ako'y isang mag-aaral ng A.L.I.V.E. (Participant 3, lines 224-225)

I help by obeying and wearing the Hijab or tandong to show that I am a student of ALIVE.

Ang pinakamahasay kong kasanayan ng mga paaralan sa pagpapatupad ng programang A.L.I.V.E ay ang pagkakaroon ng magandang asal at sinsanay ang mga mag-aaral na magkaroon ng takot sa Diyos (Allah). (C7, lines 208-210)

My best practice of schools in implementing the A.L.I.V.E program is to have good manners and train the students to have the fear of God (Allah).

Learning Arabic Alphabet and Language

Learning the Arabic alphabet and language opens doors to a rich cultural heritage and facilitates more profound connections with millions of Arabic speakers worldwide. Beyond the linguistic benefits, it offers insights into Islamic traditions, literature, and history, enabling a greater appreciation and understanding of this diverse and influential global language (Puskás & Andersson, 2019).

She answered:

Ang aking pinakamahasay na kasanayan sa programang A.L.I.V.E ay ang pagtuturo ng Arabic Language kung paano sumulat at bumasa ng mga mag-aaral at aking naituro ang kaugalian ng propheta Muhammad (peace be upon him). (Participant 3, lines 214-217)

My best practice in the ALIVE program was teaching Arabic Language how to write and read students, and I was able to teach the custom of the prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him). The good thing I experienced was the proof of reading Arabic. I kept it by enduring every test that came to me, and what I did in preparation for myself was trying to understand the Arabic Language and Islamic values and put it into practice.

Pag-aaral ng pagbigkas ng Arabic alphabet. (C8, line 383)

Learning the pronunciation of the Arabic alphabet

Applying Knowledge

Applying knowledge is the bridge that connects learning to meaningful action. By actively using the information and skills we acquire, we can solve problems, innovate, and positively impact our lives and the world. The practical application of knowledge empowers individuals to grow personally and professionally, contributing to a more informed and progressive society (Bocca-Aldaqr, 2019).

Charlie replied as follows:

Pinapanatili ko sa pamamagitan ng pagtitis sa mga bawat pagsubok na dumating sa akin at ang ginawa ko bilang paghahanda sa aking sarili ay pinagsikapan kong maiintindihan ang Arabic Language at Islamic values at maisagawa ito. (Participant 3, lines 231-234)

I maintained by enduring every test that came to me. In preparation for myself, I tried to understand the Arabic Language and Islamic values and put them into practice.

Palagi kong pinag-aralan ang mga natutunan ko na hindi ko kinakalimutan ang aking mga nalalaman at nagpapaturo pa ako sa mga may alam para madagdagan pa ang aking mga kaalaman. (C7)

I have always studied what I have learned so that I do not forget what I know and I teach those who know to increase my knowledge even more

The benefits of the A.L.I.V.E program

The table explains the essential theme of the A.L.I.V.E. program's benefits, gathered from Charlie's answers regarding its implementation.

Islam Teaching

Islam teaching encompasses a comprehensive set of principles and values guiding individuals in leading righteous and purposeful lives. With a focus on faith, compassion, and social responsibility, Islam's teachings promote spiritual growth, moral development, and harmonious coexistence, fostering a sense of unity and understanding among diverse communities worldwide. As individuals embrace these teachings, they strive to embody the values of kindness, justice, and humility, positively contributing to their communities and fostering a more compassionate and interconnected global society (van der Walt & Oosthuizen, 2021).

It is evident in the verbatim as follows:

Ang benepisyong mag-aaral sa programang ito ay nalalaman nila ang kasaysayan ng prophet mula pagkabata hanggang sa siya ay naging propheta at iba pang katuruan sa Islam (Participant 3, lines 241-243)

The benefit of the students in this program is that they know the history of the prophet from childhood until he became a prophet and other teachings in Islam. I learned the five pillars of Islam and other teachings of Islam because of this program. The benefit that I have as a student of ALIVE is that I know what I do not know about religion Islam.

Learn Valuable Strategies

Learning valuable strategies equips individuals with essential tools to navigate challenges, achieve goals, and make informed decisions. In education, career, or personal development, acquiring effective strategies empowers individuals to overcome obstacles, optimize their strengths, and adapt to ever-changing circumstances. Continuously seeking and applying valuable strategies enhances one's problem-solving abilities and leads to personal growth and a greater sense of self-efficacy, ultimately paving the way for success and fulfillment in various aspects of life (Miligan, 2018).

The following is seen in the verbatim:

Ang aking pag-aaral/tuklas na nakuha ko bilang isang mag-aaral ng A.L.I.V.E lalo na sa panahon ng pandemya ay nahihirapan ako sa par-aaral ng mga modules dahil sa walang face to face (Participant 3, lines 251-253)

My learning/discovery as a student of A.L.I.V.E, especially during the pandemic, is that I need help studying the modules because there is no face-to-face.

Ang aking diskarte ay ang pagiging masigasig ako upang magtagumpay at makamtan ang mga benepisyong A.L.I.V.E. Gusto kong ibahagi na ang pag-aaral ng A.L.I.V.E ay ang malaking benepisyong na maidudulot sa buhay ko. (C7)

My approach is to be passionate about succeeding and reaping the benefits of A.L.I.V.E. I want to share that learning A.L.I.V.E has been a great benefit to my life

Application of Learning

The application of learning is the key to unlocking the true potential of knowledge. When we actively apply what we have learned through practical experiences or real-world scenarios, we deepen our understanding, refine our skills, and reinforce our memory. By using our knowledge in meaningful ways, we enrich our lives and contribute to the betterment of society, driving progress, innovation,

and positive change in the world around us (Fadhilaatika, 2022).

It is evident in the verbatim as follows:

Sa pamamagitan ng pagsagawa ng lahat ng aking napag-aralan sa A.L.I.V.E tulad ng pagsuot ng Hijab at pagdarasal ng limang beses sa isang araw. (Participant 3, lines 255-256)

By doing everything I learned in ALIVE, such as wearing the Hijab and praying five times a day.

Always na ako naga dasal kay Allah para gabayan po nya ako. (C8)

I have always prayed to Allah to guide me.

The Opportunities to Improve the Implementation of the A.L.I.V.E Program

The table below discusses the essential theme of the opportunities to improve the implementation of the ALIVE program.

Upgrade Education

Upgrade education is a vital endeavor that involves continuous improvement and innovation in teaching methodologies, curricula, and educational systems. By incorporating cutting-edge technologies, fostering critical thinking, and promoting creativity, upgrading education equips students with the skills needed to thrive in a rapidly evolving world. This approach not only enhances individual learning outcomes but also contributes to the advancement of society, as well-prepared and empowered individuals become the driving force behind progress and positive transformation (Gamon & Tagoranao, 2022).

It is evident in the verbatim as follows:

Ang maibabahagi ng mga kalahok upang mapabuti ang pagpapatupad ng programang A.L.I.V.E ay maging maayos at Mabuti ang pamamalakad ng programang ito lalo na sa mga batang Bangsamoro. (Participant 3, lines 264-266)

What the participants can share to improve the implementation of the A.L.I.V.E program is to make this program run smoothly and well, especially for Bangsamoro children.

Ibahagi ko sa kanila ang lahat ng kabutihan at kaalaman na natutunan ko sa mga kalahok upang mapabuti ang pagpapatupad ng programang A.L.I.V.E. (C7)

I will share with them all the goodness and knowledge that I have learned from the participants to improve the implementation of the A.L.I.V.E program.

Self-Development

Self-development is a lifelong personal growth and improvement journey, encompassing acquiring new knowledge, skills, and perspectives. By actively investing in self-awareness, setting meaningful goals, and embracing challenges, individuals can unlock their full potential, cultivate resilience, and lead more fulfilling and purposeful lives. The process of self-development empowers individuals to become the best version of themselves, contributing positively to their well-being and making a meaningful impact on the world around them (Mubarak, 2021).

Moreover, self-development is an ongoing journey dedicated to personal growth and continuous improvement, involving the acquisition of new knowledge, skills, and perspectives. This journey requires a proactive approach, where individuals consciously invest in self-awareness to understand their strengths, weaknesses, and areas for growth. By setting meaningful and attainable goals, individuals can chart a clear path for their personal development, ensuring that each step they take aligns with their broader aspirations (Gamon & Tagoranao, 2022).

Charlie replied as follows:

Ang aking pinakamahusay na kagawian na maari kong ibahagi sa ibang mag-aaral ay pag-aral natin ng Mabuti ang Arabic Language at Islamic Values at maisagawa natin sa abot ng ating makakaya ang mga katuruan sa Islam. (Participant 3, lines 283-285)

The best practice I can share with other students is that we study the Arabic Language and Islamic Values well and practice Islamic teachings as much as possible.

Pagrespeto at pagtutulongan. Ang pagtutulongan at pagrespeto sa isa't-isa po. Ang mga nakatapos sa pag-aral ng A.L.I.V.E ay nakikita ko po karamihan sa kanila ay mababait at respetado po. (C8)

Respect and cooperation. Cooperation and mutual respect. Those who have completed the study of A.L.I.V.E, I see most of them are kind and respected

Socialization

Socialization is the basic process by which people pick up and assimilate the customs, beliefs, and actions of their community. It is essential for forming a person's identity, social skills, and capacity to function in various social situations. Individuals build relationships, foster empathy, and develop a sense of belonging by engaging in social interactions, ultimately contributing to the cohesiveness and harmony of communities and societies (Nurzannah et al., 2020).

She said:

Pinalawak ang aking pang-unawa sa iba't ibang indibidwal sa mga tuntunin ng multi-kultural at pagkakaiba-iba. Nakapagbigay ako ng magagandang halaga na tutulong sa akin na makihalubilo at bumuo ng magandang relasyon sa iba (Participant 3, lines 47, 50).

Expanded my understanding of different individuals in terms of multi-cultural and diversity. I instilled good values to help me socialize and build good relationships with others.

Mapabuti ang A.L.I.V.E magkaisa at magtutulongan ang mga mag-aaral. Magtutulongan po sa nakakabuting gawain at magkaisa para makabasa rin ang iba ng A.L.I.V.E. (C8)

A.L.I.V.E will improve together and students will work together. Let's work together in a good work and unite so that others can also read A.L.I.V.E.

Table 3. Best Practices, Benefits, and Opportunities to Improve the School in the Implementation of the ALIVE Program

<i>Clustered Themes</i>	<i>Emergent Themes</i>
Best Practices	
Teachers should have a personal classroom.	Developing Conducive Environment
A personal prayer room would be of great help in delivering quality education.	
Show good morals towards others	Adapting Good Values
Respect diversity of culture, belief, and religion	
Encouraged to read Arabic and memorize Surah or verses of Qur-an	Learning Arabic Alphabet and Language
Arabic Alphabet and Language	
Learned to read the Arabic alphabet	
Apply the values that they have learned in the ALIVE program	Applying Knowledge
Practice what they had learned even outside the school premises	
Benefits	
Able to share the Islamic teaching with the learners	Islam Teaching
A to value the Islam teaching more	
Have discovered a lot of valuable insights related to Islam teaching	Learn Valuable Strategies
Able to learn about the history of the prophets and the value of Islam	
Learned many strategies like how to become hardworking, persistent, patient, and other good qualities	
Were taught how to study hard and do their best while learning the ALIVE program	Application of Learning
We're able to apply their learning in real-life situations	
Applied the teachings in the ALIVE program, like wearing their Hijab properly and praying constantly	
Learned to abide by the rules and regulations set by the school through the help of the ALIVE program	Upgrade Education
Opportunities to Improve	
Help learners achieve excellent quality of education	Self-Development
Expose ALIVE teachers to training and seminars	
Hire more qualified ALIVE teachers	Socialization
Help learners strive to become a good role model	
Develop intrapersonal skills	
Develop oneself by helping others and showing respect	
Maintain collaborative relationships	
Reach-out with others	

7. CASE 4 - DELTA

Delta is a 12-year-old male, Grade 6 learner of Barongis Elementary School who is currently enrolled in the Arabic Language and Islamic Values Education (A.L.I.V.E.) program.

Best Practices of the Schools in the Implementation of A.L.I.V.E Program

The table below describes the essential themes gathered about the schools' best practices in implementing the A.L.I.V.E. program. Moreover, core ideas are also presented based on the participant's responses.

Developing Conducive Environment

A conducive environment is essential for fostering growth, learning, and innovation. Whether in educational institutions, workplaces, or communities, creating a supportive and encouraging atmosphere empowers individuals to thrive, collaborate, and achieve their fullest potential (Sattar & Arriola, 2020).

The following is seen in the verbatim:

Paglilinis at pagtulong. (Participant 4, lines 306)

Cleaning and Helping

Adapting Good Values

Adapting good values is a fundamental aspect of personal and societal development. Embracing ethical principles, empathy, respect, and compassion contributes to individual well-being and cultivates a harmonious and compassionate community where people can coexist positively and constructively. Commitment to good values guides decision-making, fostering stronger relationships and promoting a healthier and more prosperous society (Setiawan, 2020).

It is evident in the verbatim as follows:

Nalaman ko ang mabuting aral sa Islam at yong mga ipinagbabawal sa Islam. (Participant 4, lines 312-313)

I learned the suitable lessons in Islam and those forbidden in Islam. I have shown the good Muslim.

Ang pinakamahusay na kasanayan ng mga paaralan sa pagpapatupad ng programang A.L.I.V.E ay ang pagkakaroon ng magandang asal at manatili ang takot kay Allah. Ang mabubuting gawi na aking naranasan ay ang pagiging seryuso sa pag-aaral para madaling maintindihan ang mga itinuturo sa akin ng mga A.L.I.V.E teacher. (D11, lines 132-134)

The best practice of schools in implementing the A.L.I.V.E program is to have good manners and remain fearing Allah. The good habits that I have experienced are being serious about learning so that I can easily understand what the A.L.I.V.E teachers are teaching me.

Learning Arabic Alphabet and Language

Learning the Arabic alphabet and language opens doors to a rich cultural heritage and facilitates more profound connections with millions of Arabic speakers worldwide. Beyond the linguistic benefits, it offers insights into Islamic traditions, literature, and history, enabling a greater appreciation and understanding of this diverse and influential global language (Shafaghat et al., 2018).

He said:

Mag-aaral ng mabuti para maintindihan ang lahat na itinuturo ng mga ustadz/asatidz. (Participant 4, lines 308-309)

Study hard to understand everything taught by the ustadz/asatidz.

Ang pinakamahusay kong kasanayan sa programang A.L.I.V.E ay ang pagsasanay sa pagsulat at pagbasa ng Arabic Alphabet sa paaralan at sa bahay. (D11, lines 208-210)

My best practice in the A.L.I.V.E program is practicing writing and reading the Arabic Alphabet at school and at home

Applying Knowledge

Applying knowledge is the bridge that connects learning to meaningful action. By actively using the information and skills we acquire, we can solve problems, innovate, and positively impact our lives and the world. The practical application of knowledge empowers individuals to grow personally and professionally, contributing to a more informed and progressive society (Tolchah & Mu'ammam, 2019).

Delta replied as follows:

Lahat ng Natutunan ko sa A.L.I.V.E ay ginawa ko tulad ng pagbigkas ng Bismillah bako ako matulog, kumain, maligo at iba pa (Participant 4, lines 323-324)

Everything I learned in ALIVE I did like reciting Bismillah, I didn't sleep, eat, take a bath and so on.

Magbasa palagi, hindi magliban sa klase, magtanong palagi kapag-hindi alam at magsulat palagi. (D10)

Always read, never miss class, always ask questions when you don't know and always write

The Benefits of the A.L.I.V.E Program

The table explains the essential theme of the benefits of the A.L.I.V.E. program gathered from Delta's answers regarding its implementation.

Islam Teaching

Islam's teachings encompass a comprehensive set of principles and values that guide individuals in leading righteous and purposeful lives. With a focus on faith, compassion, and social responsibility, Islam's teachings promote spiritual growth, moral development, and harmonious coexistence, fostering a sense of unity and understanding among diverse communities worldwide. As individuals embrace these teachings, they strive to embody the values of kindness, justice, and humility, positively contributing to their communities and fostering a more compassionate and interconnected global society (Fuadi & Suyatno, 2020).

It is evident in the verbatim as follows:

Nalaman ko ang mabuting aral sa Islam at yong mga ipinagbabawal sa Islam. (Participant 4, lines 312-313)

I learned the good lessons in Islam and those forbidden in Islam.

Nagka alam din sa Islam kunti ganon din si tatay at nanay naka aral kami ng Islam. Naka alam kami sa Islam magsambayang, magsulat, magbasa ng Arabic at na alam naming si propheta Muhammad. Naka aral ako ng Islam at ano ang ibig sabihin na Muslim. Sana mag-aral din sila ng A.L.I.V.E para mayroon din sila alam sa Islam. (D10)

I also knew a little about Islam, but my father and mother also taught us Islam. In Islam, we know how to worship, write, read Arabic and we know prophet Muhammad. I learned about Islam and what it means to be a Muslim. I hope they also study A.L.I.V.E so that they also know something about Islam

Learn Valuable Strategies

Learning valuable strategies equips individuals with essential tools to navigate challenges, achieve goals, and make informed decisions. In education, career, or personal development, acquiring effective strategies empowers individuals to overcome obstacles, optimize their strengths, and adapt to ever-changing circumstances. Continuously seeking and applying valuable strategies enhances one's problem-solving abilities and leads to personal growth and a greater sense of self-efficacy, ultimately paving the way for success and fulfillment in various aspects of life (Lamla, 2018).

The following is seen in the verbatim:

Dapat maging masipag sa pag-aaral ng A.L.I.V.E. (Participant 4, lines 343)

Must be diligent in learning ALIVE.

Ang aking diskarte ay ang pagiging masipag, masigasig at mahaba ang pasensya upang makamitan ko ang mga benepisyo ng programang A.L.I.V.E dahil alam ko ito ang makakabuti sa akin balang araw. Nakakaapekto rin ito sa akin sa pang araw-araw na benepisyo bilang isang mag-aaral pero kaylangan ko magsikap para mapabuti aking buhay. Ang pag-aaral sa A.L.I.V.E ay may malaking benepisyo na maidudulot sa buhay ko. (D11)

My approach is to be hardworking, enthusiastic and patient enough to reap the benefits of the A.L.I.V.E program because I know it will benefit me one day. It also affects my daily benefits as a student but I have to work hard to improve my life. Studying at A.L.I.V.E has had great benefits in my life

Application of Learning

The application of learning is the key to unlocking the true potential of knowledge. When we actively apply what we have learned through practical experiences or real-world scenarios, we deepen our understanding, refine our skills, and reinforce our memory. By using our knowledge in meaningful ways, we enrich our lives and contribute to the betterment of society, driving progress, innovation, and positive change in the world around us (Abram et al., 2020).

Delta answered as follows:

Mag-aaral ng Mabuti sa A.L.I.V.E para hindi ka maging ignorante sa Islam. (Participant 4, lines 344-345)

Study well for a bright future. Study well in ALIVE so you do not become ignorant of Islam.

Ang gusto kong ibahagi ay mag-aaral ng mabuti para matugunan ang benepisyo ng programang A.L.I.V.E. (D12)

What I want to share is to study hard to meet the benefit of the A.L.I.V.E program.

The opportunities to improve the Implementation of the A.L.I.V.E Program

The table below discusses the essential theme of the opportunities to improve the implementation of the ALIVE program.

Upgrade Education

Upgrade education is a vital endeavor that involves continuous improvement and innovation in teaching methodologies, curricula, and educational systems. By incorporating cutting-edge technologies, fostering critical thinking, and promoting creativity, upgrading

education equips students with the skills needed to thrive in a rapidly evolving world (Abdulkarim & Suud, 2020).

The following is seen in the verbatim:

Dagdagan ang aming mga A.L.I.V.E materials para makapagsikap kami lalo sa pag-aaral (Participant 4, lines 351-352)

Increase our ALIVE materials so we can work harder in learning. We have ALIVE modules. I wish we had our classroom so we could study adequately.

Mag-aaral ng mabuti upang matugunan ang hamon na naranasan programang A.L.I.V.E. Ang mungkahi ko sa ibang mag-aaral ay hindi mag-absent at makinang sa mga itinuturo sa paaralan. (D12)

Study hard to meet the challenge experienced program A.L.I.V.E. My suggestion to other students is not to be absent and be brilliant in what is taught in school

Self-Development

Self-development is a lifelong personal growth and improvement journey that encompasses acquiring new knowledge, skills, and perspectives. By actively investing in self-awareness, setting meaningful goals, and embracing challenges, individuals can unlock their full potential, cultivate resilience, and lead more fulfilling and purposeful lives. The process of self-development empowers individuals to become the best version of themselves, contributing positively to their well-being and making a meaningful impact on the world around them (Puskás & Andersson, 2019).

He said:

Sa panahon ng pandemya natuto rim ako mula sa mga modules na ibinigay ng mga A.L.I.V.E Teachers (Participant 4, 338-339)

During the pandemic I also learned from the modules provided by ALIVE Teachers.

Ang maibahagi ko sa kanila ay ang lahat ng kabutihan at kaalaman na natutunan sa mga kalahok upang mapabuti ang paglaganap at ang pagpapatupad ng programang A.L.I.V.E. Magsikap at magtiwala palagi sa sarili mapabuti ang pag-aaral sa A.L.I.V.E program. (D11)

What I can share with them is all the goodness and knowledge learned from the participants to improve the spread and the implementation of the A.L.I.V.E program. Always work hard and believe in yourself to improve your studies in the A.L.I.V.E program

Socialization

Socialization is the basic process by which how people pick up and assimilate their community's customs, beliefs, and actions. It is essential for forming a person's identity, social skills, and capacity to function in various social situations. By engaging in social interactions, individuals build relationships, foster empathy, and develop a sense of belonging, ultimately contributing to the cohesiveness and harmony of communities and societies.

Delta replied the following verbatim:

Masaya mag-aral sa A.L.I.V.E. (Participant 4, line 359)

It is fun to study A.L.I.V.E.

Magtulong ako para sa ikakabuti ng programang A.L.I.V.E at ipamahagi ko rin sa iba ang mabubuting asal na natutunan ko. (D11)

I will help for the good of the A.L.I.V.E program and I will also share the good manners I have learned with others.

Table 4. Best Practices, Benefits, and Opportunities to Improve the School in the Implementation of the ALIVE Program

Clustered Themes	Emergent Themes
Best Practices	
Teachers should have a personal classroom.	Developing Conductive Environment
A personal prayer room would be of great help in delivering quality education.	
Show good morals towards others	
Respect diversity of culture, belief, and religion	Adapting Good Values
Encouraged to read Arabic and memorize Surah or verses of Qur-an	
Arabic Alphabet and Language	Learning Arabic Alphabet and Language
Learned to read the Arabic alphabet	
Apply the values that they have learned in the ALIVE program	
Practice what they had learned even outside the school premises	Applying Knowledge
Benefits	
Able to share the Islamic teaching with the learners	Islam Teaching

A to value the Islam teaching more	
Have discovered a lot of valuable insights related to Islam teaching	
Able to learn about the history of the prophets and the value of Islam	
Learned many strategies like how to become hardworking, persistent, patient, and other good qualities	Learn Valuable Strategies
Were taught how to study hard and do their best while learning the ALIVE program	
We're able to apply their learning in real-life situations	
Applied the teachings in the ALIVE program, like wearing their Hijab properly and praying constantly	Application of Learning
Learned to abide by the rules and regulations set by the school through the help of the ALIVE program	
Opportunities to Improve	
Help learners achieve excellent quality of education	
Expose ALIVE teachers to training and seminars	Upgrade Education
Hire more qualified ALIVE teachers	
Help learners strive to become a good role model	
Develop intrapersonal skills	Self-Development
Develop oneself by helping others and showing respect	
Maintain collaborative relationships	
Reach-out with others	Socialization

8. CASE 5 – ECHO

Echo is a 12-year-old male, Grade 6 learner of Barongis Elementary School who is currently enrolled in the Arabic Language and Islamic Values Education (A.L.I.V.E.) program.

Best Practices of the Schools in the Implementation of A.L.I.V.E Program

The table below describes the essential themes gathered about the schools' best practices in implementing the A.L.I.V.E. program. Moreover, core ideas are also presented based on the responses of the Echo participants.

Developing Conducive Environment

A conducive environment is essential for fostering growth, learning, and innovation. Whether in educational institutions, workplaces, or communities, creating a supportive and encouraging atmosphere empowers individuals to thrive, collaborate, and achieve their fullest potential (Javiniar, 2018).

The following is seen in the verbatim:

Cleaning the room of A.L.I.V.E class, pag-aaral ng Qur'an at pag-aaral kung paano sumulat ng Arabic Alphabet (Participant 5, lines 380-381)

Cleaning the room of the ALIVE class, studying the Qur'an, and learning how to write the Arabic Alphabet.

Adapting Good Values

Adapting good values is a fundamental aspect of personal and societal development. Embracing ethical principles, empathy, respect, and compassion contributes to individual well-being and cultivates a harmonious and compassionate community where people can coexist positively and constructively. Commitment to good values guides decision-making, fostering stronger relationships and promoting a healthier and more prosperous society (Isah & Base, 2022).

It is evident in the verbatim as follows:

Natutunan ko ang mabuting asal ng Islam at nalalaman ko kung ano ang ipinagbabawal sa Islam (Participant 5, lines 386-387).

I have learned the good manners of Islam, and I know what is forbidden in Islam.

Pinakamahasay na kasanayan ng mga paaralan sa pagpapatupad ng programang A.L.I.V.E ay ang pagkatuto ng magandang asal at sinasanay ang mga mag-aaral na magkaroon ng may paniniwala at pagsunod sa utos ng Allah. Pinakamahasay na kasanayan sa programang A.L.I.V.E ay masanay ng mahabang pasensya upang matuto ng mabuti. (E13, lines 208-210)

The best practice of schools in implementing the A.L.I.V.E program is to teach good manners and train students to have faith in and obey the commandments of Allah. Best practice in the A.L.I.V.E program is to practice patience to learn well

Learning Arabic Alphabet and Language

Learning the Arabic alphabet and language opens doors to a rich cultural heritage and facilitates more profound connections with millions of Arabic speakers worldwide. Beyond the linguistic benefits, it offers insights into Islamic traditions, literature, and history, enabling a greater appreciation and understanding of this diverse and influential global language (Ayangco-Derramas, 2022).

Echo said:

Bago pa ako nagaral ng A.L.I.V.E ay di pa ako marunong sumulat at bumasa ng nakapag-aral na ako ay natuto na ako. (Participant 5, lines 393-394)

I am learning how to write and read Arabic Alphabet. Teaching the subject of Arabic Language and Islamic Values.

Ang kasanayan ng paaralan sa programang A.L.I.V.E ay napapaturong rin sa mga magulang paano magbasa at magsulat ng Arabic. (E14)

The school's practice in the A.L.I.V.E program also teaches parents how to read and write Arabic.

Applying Knowledge

Applying knowledge is the bridge that connects learning to meaningful action. By actively using the information and skills we acquire, we can solve problems, innovate, and positively impact our lives and the world. The practical application of knowledge empowers individuals to grow personally and professionally, contributing to a more informed and progressive society (Isah & Base, 2022).

He replied the following:

Inihahanda ko ang aking sarili mula sa mga natutunan ko sa A.L.I.V.E tulad ng pagbigkas ng Bismillah bago kumain, umalis ng bahay at pag-nakauwi na ako ay sasabihin ko ang Alhamdulillah. (Participant 5, lines 397-399)

I prepare myself from what I learned in ALIVE, such as reciting Bismillah before eating, leaving the house, and when I get home, I will say Alhamdulillah.

Ginagawa ang lahat ng mga natutunan ko araw-araw yong mga magagandang pag-uugali at paggalang sa kapwa. (E15)

Doing all the things I learned every day, good manners and respect for others.

The benefits of the A.L.I.V.E program

The table explains the essential theme of the benefits of the A.L.I.V.E. program gathered by Echo's answers regarding its implementation.

Islam Teaching

Islam's teachings encompass a comprehensive set of principles and values that guide individuals in leading righteous and purposeful lives. Focusing on faith, compassion, and social responsibility, Islam's teachings promote spiritual growth, moral development, and harmonious coexistence, fostering a sense of unity and understanding among diverse communities worldwide. As individuals embrace these teachings, they strive to embody the values of kindness, justice, and humility, positively contributing to their communities and fostering a more compassionate and interconnected global society (Kooria, 2022).

It is evident in the verbatim as follows:

Natututo ako sa mga kapwa kong mag-aaral kung papaano gumalang at nagbibigay sa akin ng saya para magpapatuloy sa pag-aaral ng A.L.I.V.E program. (Participant 5, lines 404-406)

I am learning from my fellow learners on how to be polite and it gives me happiness to continue learning in the A.L.I.V.E. program.

Ang benepisyo nito sa akin ay ang pagkakaroon ng maraming kaalaman sa Islam tulad ng mabuting pag-uugali at pagsunod sa mga kautusan ni Allah at yon ay ang pagsamba sakanya ng limang besis sa isang araw. (E14)

Its benefit to me is having a lot of knowledge in Islam such as good behavior and obeying the commandments of Allah and that is worshiping him five times a day.

Learn Valuable Strategies

Learning valuable strategies equips individuals with essential tools to navigate challenges, achieve goals, and make informed decisions. In education, career, or personal development, acquiring effective strategies empowers individuals to overcome obstacles, optimize their strengths, and adapt to ever-changing circumstances. Continuously seeking and applying valuable strategies enhances one's problem-solving abilities and leads to personal growth and a greater sense of self-efficacy, ultimately paving the way for success and fulfillment in various aspects of life (Abram et al., 2020).

The following is seen in the verbatims:

Maging masipag sa pag-aral para may ginhawa ang pamumuhay. (Participant 5, lines 411)

Be diligent in studying so that life can be comfortable.

Ang diskarte ko ay ang pagiging masipag sa pag-aaral upang matagumpay at makamitan ko ang mga benepisyo ng programang A.L.I.V.E na ito. (E13)

My strategy is to study hard so I can be successful and reap the benefits of this A.L.I.V.E program.

Application of Learning

The application of learning is the key to unlocking the true potential of knowledge. When we actively apply what we have learned through practical experiences or real-world scenarios, we deepen our understanding, refine our skills, and reinforce our memory. By using our knowledge in meaningful ways, we enrich our lives and contribute to the betterment of society, driving progress, innovation, and positive change in the world around us (Fuadi & Suyatno, 2020).

It is evident in the verbatim as follows:

Pagkatuto mula sa mga modules na ibinibigay ng mga A.L.I.V.E teachers. (Participant 5, lines 415-416)

Learning from modules provided by A.L.I.V.E. teachers.

Ang maibahagi ko na kwento sa mga mag-aaral para makuha ang benepiso ng A.L.I.V.E program ay sa panahon ng pandemya na maraming rules na sundin pero dapat din natin sumunod sa mga kautusan at pagdisiplina sa sarili upang saganon ay ligtas ang kalusugan ng buong pamilya. (E14)

The story I can share with the students to get the benefit of the A.L.I.V.E program is that during the pandemic there are many rules to follow but we must also follow the orders and self-discipline so that the health of the whole family is safe.

The Opportunities to Improve the Implementation of the A.L.I.V.E Program

The table below discusses the essential theme of the opportunities to improve the implementation of the ALIVE program.

Upgrade Education

Upgrade education is a vital endeavor that involves continuous improvement and innovation in teaching methodologies, curricula, and educational systems. By incorporating cutting-edge technologies, fostering critical thinking, and promoting creativity, upgrading education equips students with the skills needed to thrive in a rapidly evolving world. This approach not only enhances individual learning outcomes but also contributes to the advancement of society, as well-prepared and empowered individuals become the driving force behind progress and positive transformation (Fuadi & Suyatno, 2020).

He answered:

Modules ang interbensiyon para sagutin Sana may sarili kaming classroom para maka apply ang mga natutunan sa A.L.I.V.E. (Participant 5, lines 413, 443-444)

Modules are the intervention to answer. Good student. I hope we have our classroom to apply what we learned in ALIVE.

Ang gusto ko imungkahi sa ibang mag-aaral ay mag-aral ng mabuti at huwag mag-absent. (E13)

What I would like to suggest to other students is to study hard and not be absent

Self-Development

Self-development is a lifelong journey of personal growth and improvement that encompasses acquiring new knowledge, skills, and perspectives. By actively investing in self-awareness, setting meaningful goals, and embracing challenges, individuals can unlock their full potential, cultivate resilience, and lead more fulfilling and purposeful lives. The process of self-development empowers individuals to become the best version of themselves, contributing positively to their well-being and making a meaningful impact on the world around them (Fuadi & Suyatno, 2020).

Echo replied as follows:

Pagkatuto mula sa mga modules na ibinibigay ng mga A.L.I.V.E teachers. (Participant 5, lines 415-416)

Learning from modules provided by ALIVE teachers.

Ipakita ko sa kanila ang kabutihan, kahalagahan at kaalaman na natutunan ko sa mga kalahok upang mapabuti ang pagpapatupad ng programang A.L.I.V.E sa mga paaralan. Maging matatag at pahabain ang pasensya para malampasan ang mga hamon na naranasan sa pag-aaral ng programang A.L.I.V.E upang maging matagumpay ang buhay. (E13)

I will show them the goodness, importance and knowledge that I learned from the participants to improve the implementation of the A.L.I.V.E program in schools. Be strong and extend patience to overcome the challenges encountered in learning the A.L.I.V.E program to make life successful.

Socialization

Socialization is the basic process by which people pick up and assimilate the customs, beliefs, and actions of their community. It is essential for forming a person's identity, social skills, and capacity to function in various social situations. Individuals build relationships, foster empathy, and develop a sense of belonging by engaging in social interactions, ultimately contributing to the cohesiveness and harmony of communities and societies (Puskás & Andersson, 2019).

Table 5. Best Practices, Benefits, and Opportunities to Improve the School in the Implementation of the ALIVE Program

<i>Clustered Themes</i>	<i>Emergent Themes</i>
Best Practices	
Teachers should have a personal classroom.	Developing Conductive Environment
A personal prayer room would be of great help in delivering quality education.	
Show good morals towards others	Adapting Good Values
Respect diversity of culture, belief, and religion	
Encouraged to read Arabic and memorize Surah or verses of Qur-an	Learning Arabic Alphabet and Language
Arabic Alphabet and Language	
Learned to read the Arabic alphabet	Applying Knowledge
Apply the values that they have learned in the ALIVE program	
Practice what they had learned even outside the school premises	
Benefits	
Able to share the Islamic teaching with the learners	Islam Teaching
A to value the Islam teaching more	
Have discovered a lot of valuable insights related to Islam teaching	Learn Valuable Strategies
Able to learn about the history of the prophets and the value of Islam	
Learned many strategies like how to become hardworking, persistent, patient, and other good qualities	Application of Learning
Were taught how to study hard and do their best while learning the ALIVE program	
We're able to apply their learning in real-life situations	Upgrade Education
Applied the teachings in the ALIVE program, like wearing their Hijab properly and praying constantly	
Learned to abide by the rules and regulations set by the school through the help of the ALIVE program	Self-Development
Opportunities to Improve	
Help learners achieve excellent quality of education	Socialization
Expose ALIVE teachers to training and seminars	
Hire more qualified ALIVE teachers	
Help learners strive to become a good role model	
Develop intrapersonal skills	
Develop oneself by helping others and showing respect	
Maintain collaborative relationships	
Reach-out with others	

9. Similarities and Differences of the Five Cases

Implementing the A.L.I.V.E. Program is essential in preparing children for academic success and global communication. This program was built on an Islamic perspective and enhanced children's knowledge of their cultural and religious foundations. Thus, the parents and ustads focus on improving the implementation of the A.L.I.V.E. program to meet the children's needs in learning A.L.I.V.E. and improve their macro skills.

The data explains the similarities and differences of each of the six cases regarding their perception of the implementation of the ALIVE program. Results are based on the responses of all the participants—students, parents, and ustadz—to the first three research questions. Each identified case is related to the given categories.

Additionally, the items described in the table represent the impact of the schools on implementing practices for their ALIVE program to the children, the benefits that the program provides to the participants, and the opportunities to improve the program.

The table has three columns: the first is for the category, the second is the sample verbatim statements taken from the participants' responses, and the third is the identified cases coded as Alpha, Bravo, Charlie, Delta, and Echo.

Table 6. Similarities in the implementation of the A.L.I.V.E. program

<i>Clustered Themes</i>	<i>Emergent Themes</i>
Best Practices	

Employed with a competent and eligible Asatidz (Teacher) to provide the best learning among students.	
Teaching of an A.L.I.V.E. teacher of Arabic Language and Islamic Values Education through modular during the pandemic	Developing Conducive Environment
Teaching children properly	
Provide an opportunity to teach all students Islamic lessons and practices	
Help students learn well in the A.L.I.V.E. program	
Maintained good morals towards others	
Read Arabic and memorize Surahs or verses from the Qur'an. Recognize the only creator (Allah)	
Following and wearing a Hijab	
Learned the excellent lessons in Islam and those forbidden in Islam	Adapting Good Values
Obedying and respecting parents	
Have good manners and train students to have the fear of God (Allah)	
Teach comes from the Qur'an and Hadith	
Teaching the Arabic Language	
Writing the Arabic Alphabet and learning to read	Learning Arabic Alphabet and Language
Learning how to write and read the Arabic alphabet	
Teaching the subject of Arabic Language and Islamic Values	
Equipping and applying all the values taught every day	
Reciting Bismillah, I did not sleep, eat, take a bath, and so on	
Always studied what I learned	
Always read, never miss class, always ask questions when you do not know, and always write.	Applying Knowledge
Doing everything I learned daily, good manners and respect for others.	
Benefits	
Learned the teachings of Islam	
Know the history of the prophet	
Know about Islam	Islam Teaching
Discovered things that I did not know	
Gaining knowledge about Islam is a significant benefit for me	
To be steadfast and optimistic	
Be diligent in learning A.L.I.V.E.	
Be passionate about succeeding and achieving the A.L.I.V.E. benefits	Learn Valuable Strategies
Get the benefits of A.L.I.V.E. should be to have broad and sound knowledge	
Effort to finish my studies insha Allah	
Apply what I have learned	
Doing everything I learned in A.L.I.V.E., like wearing a Hijab and praying five times a day	Application of Learning
Study good in A.L.I.V.E. so you do not become ignorant of Islam	
Apply what they have learned in the A.L.I.V.E. program, such as good manners	
Opportunities to Improve	
Deploy more A.L.I.V.E. teachers	
Study hard to meet life's challenges	
Make this program run smoothly and well, especially for Bangsamoro children.	Upgrade Education
Work harder in learning	
Have a separate classroom, and we also have a prayer room	
By doing reading, writing, and proper teaching to help the A.L.I.V.E. program	
Being a role model to other students	
Being patient and strong	
Work hard and believe in yourself	Self-Development
Consider all the good learnings, knowledge, manners, and behavior	
Work hard and study hard	
Invite children like me to work hard in learning	
Improve the A.L.I.V.E. program, unite and work together	Socialization
Implement the good of A.L.I.V.E.	
Work together in good work and unite so that others can also read A.L.I.V.E.	

The table above describes the similarities of each participant concerning their perception of the practices being implemented by the school on the ALIVE program. The first research question explains what they considered the best practices of their respective schools for implementing the program. In this category, seven essential themes emerged.

The five cases—Alpha, Bravo, Charlie, Delta, and Echo—similarly reflect the themes of this category. Below are further explanations about the given data.

The aforementioned essential themes for this category comprise what the participants thought were their schools' best practices for implementing the ALIVE program: developing a conducive environment, adopting good values, learning the Arabic Alphabet and language, and applying knowledge.

The above table described the benefits of the ALIVE program as perceived by the participants on their respective points of view - as students, parents, and ustads. As explained by the second research question, the themes for this category comprised the program's benefits listed by the participants. Seven essential themes were considered, all of them were similarly reflected in the six cases, and they are listed as follows:

The table above explains the opportunities to improve the ALIVE program as perceived by the participants. Six emerging themes are presented in the third research question, all of which were reflected similarly in all cases identified. The themes above are upgrading education, self-development, positivity, socialization, learning to study hard, and promoting good qualities. Below is a further explanation of the essential themes for this category.

Table 7. Differences in the implementation of the A.L.I.V.E. program

<i>Clustered Themes</i>	<i>Emergent Themes</i>
Best Practices	
Have own classroom and prayer room	
Have an A.L.I.V.E. Teacher in his classroom and Musallah (Prayer room).	Developing Conducive Environment
Cleaning the room of A.L.I.V.E. class.	
Benefits	
Given the opportunity to share their knowledge in this program.	
Provide the knowledge they need to learn.	Skills are Acknowledged
Given the opportunity to teach at A.L.I.V.E...	
Have a comfortable life, so the child wants to finish school.	
Learned from studying the A.L.I.V.E. program.	Happiness
He can teach his child who studied at A.L.I.V.E.	
Opportunities to Improve	
Continue to give full support so that the A.L.I.V.E. program is good	
Encourage parents of A.L.I.V.E. students to unite to support the A.L.I.V.E. program	
Improve the implementation of this program	Provide Full Support
Implement the A.L.I.V.E. program	

The above table describes the differences of each participant regarding their opinions on their schools' best practices for implementing the ALIVE program. The first research question has two essential themes identified by different participant groups: employing training and seminars and developing a conducive environment.

The themes above for this category are similarly reflected in the four cases: Alpha (A2), Bravo (B4-B5), Delta (D10), and Foxtrot (F.G.D. U1). Below are further explanations about the given data.

Developing a Conducive Environment. The participants considered having a conducive environment for learning would be of great importance to implementing the ALIVE program, as this would enable the children to learn on a steadfast pace. A conducive environment includes enough facilities, up-to-date equipment and materials, warm and lively homerooms, and a separate prayer room.

The above table describes each group's differences regarding what they perceived as the benefits of the ALIVE program. It answered the second research question and resulted in two essential themes identified in different participant groups. These skills are acknowledged and happy. Only two groups of participants participated in these themes: the B and F groups.

Skills are acknowledged. Beta Group (4-5) considered the teachers' skills in teaching the subjects under the ALIVE program to benefit their education since these teachers could impart their knowledge and learnings to the students.

Happiness. The Foxtrot group acknowledged happiness as a benefit of the program for their teaching experience and parenting journey. Some consider the program an opportunity to widen their knowledge and impart it to the students. Moreover, parents considered happiness a benefit due to the impact of the ALIVE program in their daily lives and how it relieved them that their children were in good hands and on their way to reaching their goals.

The above table describes the differences between each group in terms of what they considered opportunities to improve the implementation of the ALIVE program. It answered the third research question and resulted in only one essential theme: providing full support, which is only reflected in two groups of participants.

Provide full support. To fully implement the ALIVE program, participants believed full support from the government, community, teachers, parents, and students was suggested. The government should provide a budget and support for the program to monitor the qualifications of teachers and the conducive environment for the students. Parents should monitor their children and their competencies to ensure valuable learning. The unity of the population above towards the program would ensure its viability and long-term efficiency.

Discussion

This part discusses significant findings, summary, and conclusions from the themes that surfaced from data analysis. Five participants were involved in this qualitative study: Alpha, Bravo, Charlie, Delta, and Echo. All participants were Grade 6 learners enrolled in the Arabic Language and Islamic Values Education (A.L.I.V.E.) program.

10.1. Major Findings

After an in-depth analysis of the data gathered, the following findings were drawn:

The Best Practices of Schools in the Implementation of the A.L.I.V.E. Program

It was revealed that the schools' best practices for implementing the A.L.I.V.E. program contain four emergent themes: developing a conducive environment, adopting good values, learning the Arabic Alphabet and language, and applying knowledge.

Developing Conducive Environment

All of the participants believed that the schools were able to provide quality education in implementing the program to the best of their capabilities, with ALIVE teachers teaching the students valuable knowledge and catering to their needs, especially during the pandemic when the program provided a modular alternative to learning. Above all, they believed that the mere opportunity to learn education from an Islamic perspective was enough to consider the ALIVE program a significant part of the country's educational sector.

Additionally, in the framework of Islam, education is viewed as a process that incorporates the entire individual, including the logical, spiritual, and social elements. The comprehensive and integrated approach to Islamic education, according to Syed Muhammad al-Naquib al-Attas in 1979, aims to balance the growth of the total personality through training Man's spirit, mind, rational self, feelings, and physical senses such that faith is infused into every aspect of his personality. Knowledge is learned in Islamic educational thought to actualize and perfect all facets of the human being. The prophet Muhammad is the highest and most valuable model of perfection from an Islamic perspective, and the purpose of Islamic education is for people to live as he did (Abram et al., 2020; Gomez et al., 2019; Rosyada, 2021).

Furthermore, the curriculum should incorporate various teaching strategies and materials, such as textbooks, workbooks, videos, and other multimedia resources. These materials should be designed to engage students and help them develop a deep understanding of the language and values being taught. In addition to the curriculum, it is essential to consider the training needs of teachers responsible for delivering the ALIVE program. Teachers should receive specialized training to teach Arabic language and Islamic values effectively. This training should cover classroom management, teaching strategies, and assessment methods (Fadhilaatika, 2022; Gamon & Tagoranao, 2022; Gomez et al., 2019).

In addition, ongoing evaluation and assessment are critical to ensuring the effectiveness of the ALIVE program. Student development should be regularly assessed to spot areas for further help. In order to make sure that the program continues to suit the requirements of students and aid in their development of a thorough grasp of Arabic language and Islamic beliefs, the curriculum and teaching methodologies may be improved with the help of this input. Another essential aspect to consider in implementing ALIVE is the cultural and social context in which the program will be delivered. It includes considering students' diversity in terms of their language backgrounds, cultural identities, and religious beliefs. Ensuring that the program is culturally responsive and inclusive is essential, considering all students' diverse needs and experiences (Mubarak, 2021; Nurzannah et al., 2020; Sattar & Arriola, 2020).

Adapting good values

Aside from the academic competencies, the participants maintained good morals towards others. The ALIVE program teaches education from an Islamic perspective and about respecting diversity and cultural and religious differences. The ALIVE program also teaches about the Islamic way of life and what the Quran states about the path of an ideal Muslimah.

Consequently, DepEd is implementing the Madrasah Education Program in response to the appeal for a global commitment to Education for All. The Roadmap for Improving Muslim Basic Education serves as its guidance. The Roadmap is divided into three main sections: Arabic Language and Islamic Values Education (ALIVE) for Muslim Out-of-School Youth (O.S.Y.) and Adults; Standard et al. in Private Madaris (Islamic Educational Institutions); and Public Schools. The Madrasah Education Program also intends to support the non-formal sector in addition to the formal sector. Muslim out-of-school adolescents and adults have been more prevalent in the nation. Studies from various fields indicate that Muslim regions have the most excellent rates of school abandonment (Javiniar, 2018; Mubarak, 2021; Puskás & Andersson, 2019).

Learning Arabic Alphabet and Language

The participants considered learning the Arabic alphabet an essential part of the ALIVE program because it teaches them how to read and write a foreign language. It in turn enhances their ability to communicate on a global scale. However, since Muslim O.S.Y.s without the appropriate skills for employment run the possibility of being recruited by radical extremist groups, this is a big worry for their education and the concerns with peace and order in these places. Programs for Muslim out-of-school youths and adults have been

developed to positively contribute to the peace process and improve the quality of life of Muslims through education and training, such as ALIVE is being implemented by the Bureau of Alternative Learning Systems (B.A.L.S.) in Alternative Learning Systems (A.L.S.), which offers dropouts continued education through the Basic Literacy Program and basic literacy programs with ALIVE to Muslim illiterates (Bocca-Aldaqr, 2019; Lamla, 2018; van der Walt & Oosthuizen, 2021).

Furthermore, collaboration and engagement with parents and the wider community can also be a critical factor in the success of the ALIVE program. Parents and community members can provide valuable input and support and be influential advocates for the program. Outreach efforts can include parent-teacher conferences, community meetings, and other opportunities to engage with families and community members. The ALIVE curriculum can complement extracurricular activities, including clubs, cultural events, community service initiatives, and classroom-based education. These exercises can help students apply what they have learned in real-world situations while reinforcing the morals and linguistic skills they have mastered in the classroom (Fuadi & Suyatno, 2020; Setiawan, 2020; Shafaghat et al., 2018).

Relatively, ensuring that the ALIVE program is integrated into the broader education system and recognized as a legitimate and valuable component of a well-rounded education is essential. It can involve building partnerships with other schools, universities, and educational organizations and advocating for the inclusion of Arabic language and Islamic values education in national and regional education policies. By taking a comprehensive and collaborative approach to implementing ALIVE, we can guarantee that pupils get a top-notch education that equips them for success in the contemporary world (Al Shlowiy, 2022; Rosyada, 2021; Tolchah & Mu'ammam, 2019).

Applying knowledge

Participant considered the learnings and values of the ALIVE program as something they could embody and apply in their daily lives. Even a simple phrase Bismillah every before tasks like eating, taking a bath, or sleeping was something the participants learned from the program which they applied to their lives.

Moreover, Arabic Language and Islamic Values Education with Technical-Vocational Education and Training was established with T.E.S.D.A. to provide skill training programs with ALIVE to Muslim O.S.Y.s and adults based on their interests and aptitudes. Priority in program implementation is given to migrant Muslim O.S.Y.s in urban and rural areas; ALIVE with Entrepreneurship will be developed and implemented in collaboration with T.E.S.D.A. to provide Muslim out-of-school youth and adults with skills and opportunities for livelihood; A Memorandum of Agreement between DepED and T.E.S.D.A. for T.V.E.T. with ALIVE was signed in 2007. The program's implementation guidelines are incorporated in the abovementioned M.O.A. (Hudzaifah et al., 2021; Ikhlas et al., 2021; Sattar & Arriola, 2020).

Further, Madrasah Education was the only organization that allowed Islam to survive in the Philippines during the Moro rebellion against the conquerors. Madrasah was the exclusive kind of instruction available during the Spanish Empire. In Mindanao, Sulu, and Palawan, the Western secular education system was implemented during the American era. The Western educational model was, however, rejected by the Moro Muslims because they believed it would convert their students to Christianity. It took time for Moro Muslims to adopt the secular educational system in public (government) schools (Abdulkarim & Suud, 2020; Mubarak, 2021; Puskás & Andersson, 2019).

In addition, following the proclamation of independence and amid Mindanao's large influx of Christian immigrants, the number of Moro Muslims enrolled in public schools rose dramatically. At this time, it was greater than 90%. The Madrasah educational system evolved when the Moro were sent to study in the Muslim nations in the 1950s. After returning from studying overseas, they built formal madrasah institutions in the Philippines, delivering the same Islamic sectarian curriculum (Ayangco-Derramas, 2022; Harad & Arriola, 2022; Milligan, 2018; Rosyada, 2021).

The Benefits of the A.L.I.V.E. Program

It was revealed that the benefits of the A.L.I.V.E. program have three emergent themes: Islam teaching, valuable learning strategies, and application of learning.

Islam Teaching

The core values and knowledge being taught in the ALIVE program are all about education from an Islamic perspective. The program not only focuses on the academic prospects of Islam but also teaches students about the values and Islamic way of life as stated in the Quran. It includes learning about prophets, what is right and wrong, what is permissible, and what deeds are considered reasonable and rewarded. It will help the students to strive to become an ideal Muslim.

The establishment of the madrasah, or Islamic school, in the Philippines is thought to have occurred at the same time as the spread of Islam, which was brought by Malay explorers and Arab missionaries who landed in Sulu and western Mindanao. According to the Sulu Genealogy, a certain Tuan Mashaika landed in Sulu in the 13th century and converted the locals to Islam. In the second part of the 14th century, a later missionary named Karim-ul-Makhdum arrived, and his religious activities strengthened the expanding Islamic population in Sulu (Abubakar). A decade or two after Makhdum, Rajah Baguinda, a Muslim prince from Sumatra, established himself

in the local Sulu hierarchy and promoted the dissemination of Islam (Lamla, 2018; Sali, 2021).

On the other hand, DepEd Order No.51, s. 2004 was yet another law that the Department of Education just enacted. The Madrasah Education Program for Filipino Muslim Learners was created in 2004. The abovementioned regulation required public and private Madaris to adopt the standard Madrasah Curriculum Framework. The number of schools using the curriculum has increased over the previous five years as DepEd has continued to offer materials, teacher capacity-building programs, transition support for the private Madaris, and advocacy for the program across all areas. The Madrasah Education Program was developed to give Muslim children a high-quality education that meets their needs, lays a solid foundation for their knowledge and abilities, and instills in them Islamic principles that would help them face the difficulties of modern society (Ayangco-Derramas, 2022; DepEd Order No.51, s. 2004; Lamla, 2018).

Learn valuable strategies

The ALIVE program also enables its students to learn about valuable strategies that can be applied to their daily lives. It includes being steadfast and optimistic, passionate about learning, and a goal-oriented person that would enable them to achieve their dreams and goals in life.

In addition, following the proclamation of independence and amid Mindanao's large influx of Christian immigrants, the number of Moro Muslims enrolled in public schools rose dramatically. At this time, it is greater than 90%. The Madrasah educational system evolved when the Moro were sent to study in the Muslim nations in the 1950s. After returning from studying overseas, they built formal madrasah institutions in the Philippines, delivering the same Islamic sectarian curriculum (Harad & Arriola, 2022; Milligan, 2018; Rosyada, 2021).

Application of learning

Almost all participants considered the learnings of the ALIVE program as insight into Islam's way of life, and they had to apply it to their lives. Some participants mentioned trying to live as an ideal Muslim by wearing a Hijab, practicing salah, and respecting their parents.

Madrasah Education is the only organization that allowed Islam to survive in the Philippines during the Moro rebellion against the conquerors. Madrasah was the exclusive kind of instruction available during the Spanish Empire. In Mindanao, Sulu, and Palawan, the Western secular education system was implemented during the American era. The Western educational model was, however, rejected by the Moro Muslims because they believed it would convert their students to Christianity. It took time for Moro Muslims to adopt the secular educational system in public (government) schools (Abdulkarim & Suud, 2020; Mubarak, 2021).

Consequently, the Arabic Language and Islamic Values Education (ALIVE) program offers numerous benefits for students, educators, and communities. Firstly, the program provides students with a deep understanding of the Arabic language, including its grammar, syntax, and vocabulary. It is a valuable skill that can help students communicate effectively with Arabic-speaking individuals and give them a competitive edge in the worldwide job market. Secondly, the ALIVE program teaches students Islamic values, ethics, and principles. It includes topics such as compassion, generosity, honesty, and respect, all essential qualities that can help students become responsible and ethical citizens. Additionally, by fostering a deeper awareness and love of Islamic cultures and customs, this curriculum may assist kids in finding their identity and feeling proud of their cultural history (Ayangco-Derramas, 2022; Isah & Base, 2022; Puskás & Andersson, 2019).

The Opportunities that the participants Can Share to Improve the Implementation of the ALIVE Program

It was revealed that three emergent themes formulated in the opportunities that the participants can share to improve the implementation of the ALIVE program are upgraded education, self-development, and socialization.

Upgrade Education

Participants believed deploying more qualified ALIVE teachers is essential to improving the program. Deploying this teacher to far-flung areas, secluded schools, and geographically isolated islands is preferable and would enable the program to reach more learners. Participants also believed that improvement of the ALIVE program would mirror the quality and budget the government provides, thus insinuating that to be a better program, the people behind them must be honest and truthful in their duties. Participants also mentioned upgrading their materials, equipment, and facilities to ensure quality education and a stress-free environment.

The Arabic Language and Islamic Values Education (ALIVE) Curriculum is integrated into the Department of Education's (DepEd) K to 12 Curriculum. It is primarily intended to supplement the needs of Muslim learners in Muslim-dominated areas and throughout the country. The Organic Act for the Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (A.R.M.M.) includes provisions for the regional government to establish an educational subsystem to perpetuate Filipino Islamic values and develop the spiritual, intellectual, social, cultural, scientific, and physical aspects of the region's people. Another legislation that strengthened and expanded the A.R.M.M.'s organic act ordered the inclusion of the ALIVE program in all public schools across the region (Nurzannah & Setiawan, 2020; Sattar & Arriola, 2020).

Further, the ALIVE program can promote cultural diversity and community social cohesion. Students can have a deeper appreciation and respect for diversity by learning about many cultures and customs, which helps lessen bias and discrimination. Additionally, the program can build bridges between different communities by providing a common language and shared values. Fourthly, the ALIVE program can also provide cross-cultural dialogue and exchange opportunities. Students studying Arabic language and Islamic values can exchange with students from other countries, promoting cultural understanding and appreciation. Additionally, the program can help to promote peaceful coexistence and understanding between people of different religions and cultural backgrounds (Abram et al., 2020; Godoy, 2018; Kooria, 2022).

Self-development

Participants considered themselves role models of the current ALIVE program. The values and learning they applied and showed others reflected and mirrored the program's teachings. Hence, being able to develop yourself to become a better person makes you a good role model, resulting in more people wanting to take part in the program as well. A better person can be identified as someone who instilled values learned from the program: being truthful, passionate, kind, and respectful.

Moreover, the A.R.M.M. was recently superseded by the Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (B.A.R.M.M.) under the Bangsamoro Organic Law (RA 11054). The B.A.R.M.M. is a parliamentary-democratic regional government with an executive and legislative branch led by the Chief Minister. The education sector under the B.A.R.M.M. system was combined into a single organization called the Ministry of Basic, Higher, and Technical Education (M.B.H.T.E.), headed by the Minister (Al Shlowiy, 2022; Tolchah & Mu'ammam, 2019).

Hence, the A.R.M.M. was recently superseded by the Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (B.A.R.M.M.) under the Bangsamoro Organic Law (RA 11054). The B.A.R.M.M. is a parliamentary-democratic regional government with an executive and legislative branch led by the Chief Minister. The education sector under the B.A.R.M.M. system was combined into a single organization called the Ministry of Basic, Higher, and Technical Education (M.B.H.T.E.), which was headed by the Minister (Al Shlowiy, 2022; Rosyada, 2021; Tolchah & Mu'ammam, 2019).

In addition, the Philippine educational system strives to improve learning and education processes to meet the needs of every student. Because the learning process is ongoing and growing within our fundamental teaching practice, all learners must investigate any educational philosophy. We live in a fast-changing world, and the Muslim community has been damaged by extremism. Religious extremism and radicalism, multi-religious environmental deterioration, such as loss of valuable social esteem, spiritual awareness, and purpose of existence, are all urgent issues that require immediate action. There is still time to establish a knowledge base through education. Thus, there is hope (Fuadi & Suyatno, 2020; Setiawan, 2020; Shafaghat et al., 2018).

Furthermore, many religious groups in the Philippines have established and erected their institutions under legal requirements. To assist this sacred institution, the Philippine government has attempted to solve madrasah education difficulties by distributing memoranda urging the deployment of competent and quality teachers who advocate for Islamic education. The Tripoli Agreement, negotiated by the Philippine government and the Moro National Liberation Front (MNLF), established the powers of authorities in the A.R.M.M. territory (Isah & Base, 2022; Javinir, 2018; Shafaghat et al., 2018).

Socialization

Another opportunity to improve the program is to encourage other people to participate. The way to encourage others is to socialize with them and tell them about what they have learned and the values the program teaches.

The Philippine educational system strives to improve learning and education processes to meet the needs of every student. Because the learning process is ongoing and growing within our fundamental teaching practice, all learners must investigate any educational philosophy. We live in a fast-changing world, and the Muslim community has been damaged by extremism. Religious extremism and radicalism, multi-religious environmental deterioration, such as loss of valuable social esteem, spiritual awareness, and purpose of existence, are all urgent issues that require immediate action. There is still time to establish a knowledge base through education; thus, there is hope (Fuadi & Suyatno, 2020; Setiawan, 2020).

Further, implementing Arabic Language and Islamic Values Education (ALIVE) is a complex process that depends on the educational context and the program's goals. To begin with, a comprehensive curriculum development process is needed to ensure that the program aligns with the objectives of teaching Arabic language and Islamic values. This curriculum development process should involve a team of experts who are well-versed in both the Arabic language and Islamic values. The group should collaborate to determine the precise abilities and information that students must acquire, as well as the most efficient ways to impart these ideas (Ayangco-Derramas, 2022; Harad & Arriola, 2022; Milligan, 2018; Rosyada, 2021).

10.2. Implications for Practices

The following suggestions are made in case of this research, analysis, and impact:

It is encouraged that the Department of Education Division of Palimbang Sultan Kudarat may develop specialized training for ALIVE teachers to enhance their knowledge in teaching Arabic language and Islamic values to the students. It is suggested that the School

Head encourage ALIVE instructors to discuss their techniques for motivating students to apply what they have learned in and out of the classroom.

The community should allow students to explore the implementation of the ALIVE Program so that they can reap its benefits and better understand how to apply the skills they have learned outside of school. It is heartily recommended that future researchers use this study as their basis for continuing to conduct related research about exploring the implementation of the ALIVE Program, the roles they need to perform as ALIVE students, and the strategies they may use to benefit from the ALIVE program effectively.

Best Practices of the Schools in the Implementation of A.L.I.V.E. Program

Developing a Conducive Environment. The ALIVE program aims to create a conducive learning environment in school by prioritizing key aspects. These include fostering a supportive and inclusive atmosphere, providing well-trained educators with a deep understanding of the Arabic language and Islamic values, ensuring the availability of appropriate learning resources, encouraging collaborative learning and open dialogue, and establishing a respectful and tolerant environment that embraces cultural diversity. The goal is to enable learners to actively participate, appreciate the Arabic language and Islamic values, and experience personal growth while feeling valued and belonging.

Adapting Good Values. Incorporating good values into the ALIVE program is essential for the holistic development of learners in school. It can be achieved by emphasizing character education and regularly reinforcing ethical principles like kindness, empathy, integrity, and respect in the curriculum. Teachers should be positive role models and facilitate discussions promoting understanding and tolerance. Integrate community service projects and experiential learning opportunities to apply these values in real-life situations. Prioritizing the cultivation of good values empowers learners to become responsible and compassionate individuals, contributing to a harmonious and morally conscious society.

Learning Arabic Alphabet and Language. Incorporating Arabic language learning in the ALIVE program is crucial for cultural understanding. Use interactive methods, qualified instructors, and conversational practice to instill an appreciation for the language's significance and connect with Islamic heritage and global horizons. Foster cultural competence and unity among diverse communities.

Applying Knowledge. To enhance the effectiveness of the ALIVE program, prioritize the practical application of knowledge. Implement project-based learning to foster critical thinking and problem-solving. Encourage discussions and presentations to showcase understanding. Promote collaboration on community-based projects, enabling positive contributions to society. By emphasizing practical application, the ALIVE program empowers learners to become proactive, responsible individuals who value the Arabic language and Islamic values in their daily lives.

The benefits of the A.L.I.V.E. program

Islam Teaching. For practical Islam teaching in the ALIVE program, adopt a comprehensive approach fostering knowledge and understanding. Provide well-trained educators with engaging and culturally sensitive lessons aligned with contemporary values. Encourage open dialogue and critical thinking about Islamic traditions and history. Include experiential learning like mosque visits and interactions with diverse Muslim communities to appreciate Islam's cultural heritage. Emphasize a well-rounded and relevant approach to nurture respect, tolerance, and intercultural understanding among learners for a harmonious society.

Learn Valuable Strategies. To maximize the benefits of the ALIVE program, empower learners with valuable strategies. Introduce effective study techniques, time management, and goal-setting practices for learning the Arabic language and Islamic values. Encourage self-directed learning and critical reflection. Guide note-taking and resource organization. Foster a growth mindset for resilience and embracing challenges. By equipping students with these strategies, the ALIVE program empowers them to become independent, successful learners committed to the Arabic language and Islamic values while fostering personal growth and self-confidence.

Application of Learning. Encouraging active application of learning is crucial for the success of the ALIVE program. Create opportunities for practical use of Arabic language and Islamic values through cultural events, community service, and interactions with native speakers. Implement projects that foster critical thinking and problem-solving. Provide mentorship to integrate knowledge into daily lives and personal development. By emphasizing application, the ALIVE program instills a deeper appreciation for Arabic language and Islamic values, empowering learners to become confident, culturally aware individuals who embody these principles in their actions and contributions to society.

The Opportunities to Improve the Implementation of the A.L.I.V.E. Program

Upgrade Education. The ALIVE program promotes Arabic language proficiency and instills Islamic values among learners. To achieve this, it is recommended to create a supportive and inclusive environment, prioritize applying knowledge through real-world scenarios, and empower learners with valuable strategies. Additionally, integrating effective Islamic teaching, upgrading education with modern methodologies, and encouraging continuous professional development for educators will contribute to the program's success in fostering cultural awareness and personal growth among students.

Self-Development. Encouraging self-development is crucial to the ALIVE program's implementation for learners. Provide resources and workshops that promote self-awareness, emotional intelligence, and personal growth, enabling students to understand their

strengths and areas for improvement. Emphasize the value of setting meaningful goals aligned with their interests and aspirations, empowering them to take ownership of their learning journey. Facilitate mentorship and peer support to foster a positive and growth-oriented mindset, cultivating resilience and adaptability. By prioritizing self-development, the ALIVE program can equip learners with the skills and mindset necessary for continuous improvement, enabling them to become confident, responsible, and culturally aware individuals who contribute positively to their communities and the world.

Socialization. In implementing the ALIVE program, it is crucial to prioritize various aspects to ensure its success among learners. These include fostering a supportive and inclusive environment, encouraging the application of knowledge through real-world scenarios, empowering students with valuable strategies, providing effective Islam teaching, upgrading education with modern methodologies, promoting self-development, and encouraging socialization. Considering these recommendations, the ALIVE program can effectively promote Arabic language proficiency, instill Islamic values, foster cultural awareness, and empower students to become responsible and compassionate individuals who positively contribute to society.

4.2. Implications for Future Research

Based on the experiences shared by the five participants, the results or findings of this study could not draw any conclusions from other concerned and pertinent people. Therefore, to confirm and compare the significant findings, more research pertinent to this study should be conducted with other carefully chosen people at other research locations. Some future researchers may do relevant studies to discover if there are any notable variations in how participants apply their learning in the A.L.I.V.E. program.

Conclusion

This study revealed many case studies illustrating the difficulties faced by A.L.I.V.E. pupils. The long nights, mentally demanding days, financially exhausted moments, and physically weak and emotionally unstable feelings I felt while conducting this research paled in comparison to the revelations I received after finishing the manuscript. The findings of this study convinced me that, thanks to Allah, who gives me power and fearlessness, I can achieve anything. My research adviser, the panel chair and members, and my family all aided me in continuing and finishing my thesis. This research gives me a distinct perspective that helps me to completely appreciate the value of conducting research.

There are four research questions in this study. For the first research question, the best practices of the schools in implementing the A.L.I.V.E. program are promoting the developing potential of every Muslim child and encouraging all learners to appreciate, understand, accept, and respect different ethics, religion, and culture in a multicultural and diverse environment; To support, monitor, and give training for A.L.I.V.E. teachers; To support Musabaqah and seminars about Arabic language and Islamic values education. For the second research question, the students benefit from this program through learning and applying what they have learned.

For the third research question, to improve the implementation of the A.L.I.V.E. program, there should be more A.L.I.V.E. teachers to reach learners without access to this program, especially in secluded schools. To give more seminars and training; A smooth and well-managed projects for Bangsamoro children. For the fourth research question, the implementation of the A.L.I.V.E. program is all the same except in Kanipaan Elementary School; in terms of willingness to learn, Kanipaan has separate classrooms for A.L.I.V.E. classes; thus, Christian students can choose whether to attend the class or not. Unlike the other four schools, they cannot leave the classroom because of the scheduled classes in which A.L.I.V.E. classes were included.

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